

Supporting Information

Dual Photoredox and Copper Catalysis: Enantioselective 1,2-Amidocyanation of 1,3-Dienes

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1. General information

NMR spectra were recorded on AV2 400 MHz Bruker spectrometers. Chemical shifts are given in ppm. The spectra are calibrated to the residual ^1H and ^{13}C signals of the solvents. Multiplicities are abbreviated as follows: singlet (s), doublet (d), triplet (t), quartet (q), doublet-doublet (dd), multiplet (m), and broad (b). Infrared spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-4100 spectrometer. Mass spectra were determined with a Waters ACQUITY H-class UPLC/MS ACQ-SQD by electron ionization (EI positive and negative) or a Finnigan TSQ7000 by electrospray ionization (ESI+). The accurate masses were measured by the mass spectrometry service of the EPFL by ESI-TOF using a QTOF Ultima from Waters or APPI-FT-ICR using a linear ion trap Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometer from Thermo Scientific.

Materials and Methods: Unless otherwise stated, starting materials were purchased from commercial sources (Aldrich, Acros, Merck, Fluka and VWR international). More sensitive compounds were stored in a desiccator or in a glove-box if required. Solvents were purchased in HPLC quality, degassed by purging thoroughly with nitrogen and dried over activated molecular sieves of appropriate size. Alternatively, they were purged with argon and passed through alumina columns in a solvent purification system (Innovative Technology). Reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using Merck TLC silica gel 60 F254. Compounds were visualized by UV-light at 254 nm and by dipping the plates in an ethanolic ninhydrin/acetic acid solution or an aqueous potassium permanganate solution followed by heating. Flash column chromatography was performed over silica gel (230-400 mesh). The CDCl_3 used in the NMR experiments was stored over molecular sieves before use.

2. Synthesis of the 1,3 dienes

Figure S1. Dienes synthesis

Dienes **1a,s,t,u** were synthesized by Wittig reaction of the corresponding aldehydes or ketones with methyltriphenylphosphonium bromide following reported procedures.^[1-4]

Dienes **1b-r** and diene **1v** were synthesized by Wittig reaction of the corresponding aldehydes with allyltriphenylphosphonium bromide following reported procedures.^[5-9]

Diene **1w** was synthesized from pivaldehyde following a reported procedure.^[10]

Diene **1y** was synthesized in 7 steps starting from methyl isobutyrate. Ester **1y''** was synthesized via alkylation of methyl isobutyrate following a reported procedure.^[11] Aldehyde **1y'** was synthesized from ester **1y''** via a sequence of reduction and oxidation.

To a solution of **1y''** (620 mg, 2.84 mmoles, 1 equiv) in ethanol (7.13 mL) was added palladium on activated carbon (10%, 30.2 mg, 284 μmol, 0.1 equiv). The suspension was filled with H₂ (1 atm) and stirred under H₂ bubbling over 2 h at rt. The suspension was filtered over a pad of Celite and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuo.

The crude oil was dissolved in dry dichloromethane (13 mL), cooled to -78 °C, followed by addition of diisobutylaluminium hydride (1M, 8.52 mL, 8.52 mmoles, 3 equiv), and the reaction was stirred for 1 h, quenched with Rochelle salt and stirred vigorously over 12 h. The organic phase was separated, and the aqueous phase was extracted with AcOEt (2 times). The combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated under reduced pressure.

To a solution of the resulting crude mixture in dichloromethane (13 mL) at rt, were added pyridinium chlorochromate (1.84 g, 8.52 mmoles, 3 equiv) and silica gel (1.34 g). After stirring at room temperature for 1 h, the reaction mixture was filtered through a pad of Celite to provide a residue, which was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (Pentane : AcOEt = 9 :

1) to afford pure aldehyde **1y'** in 88% yield over 3 steps. The spectroscopic data matched the reported values.^[12]

Diene **1y** was synthesized from aldehyde **1y'** via Grignard reaction of allylmagnesium bromide followed by dehydration.

A flame-dried flask was charged with a solution of **1y'** (730 mg, 3.84 mmol, 1 equiv) in diethyl ether (5 mL). A solution of allylmagnesium bromide (1M in Et₂O, 4.99 mL, 4.99 mmol, 1.3 equiv) was added dropwise at 0 °C and the resulting suspension was allowed to stir for 1 h. Saturated ammonium chloride was added at 0 °C and the biphasic mixture was slowly heated to rt. After separating the organic layer, the aqueous layer was extracted with AcOEt (2 times). The combined organic layers were washed with brine, dried over sodium sulfate, filtered and concentrated in vacuum to provide 858 mg of a crude product, which was pure enough and directly submitted to the next step without purification.

The crude oil (488 mg, 2.1 mmol, 1 equiv) was dissolved in dry dichloromethane (6.66 mL), followed by successive addition of triethylamine (3.7 mL) and methanesulfonyl chloride (833 μL, 10.8 mmol, 5.12 equiv). The mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight and diluted with water. The organic phase was separated, and the aqueous phase was extracted with AcOEt (2 times). The combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated under reduced pressure.

The resulting crude oil was dissolved in toluene (10 mL), followed by addition of 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (784 μL, 5.25 mmol, 2.5 equiv), heated to reflux overnight and diluted with water. The organic phase was separated, and the aqueous phase was extracted with AcOEt (2 times). The combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated under reduced pressure to provide a residue, which was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (100% pentane) to afford 400 mg of pure diene **1y** in 85% yield over 3 steps.

Diene **1z** was synthesized via triflate protection of estrone followed by palladium catalyzed dienylation following reported procedures. The spectroscopic data matched the reported values.^[13-14]

Diene **4** was synthesized via cyclopropanation of cinnamyl alcohol, followed by oxidation and Wittig olefination following a reported procedure.^[15] The spectroscopic data matched the reported values.

3. Characterization data of unreported 1,3 dienes

Isolated as a 1:1 mixture of E/Z isomers. 400 mg, 42.5% yield (6 mmol scale). Colorless oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.41 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.33 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.11 – 7.01 (m, 4H), 6.87 (dddd, *J* = 16.9, 11.2, 10.2, 1.1 Hz, 1H), 6.74 (ddt, *J* = 15.7, 10.4, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 6.55 (br d, *J* = 15.6 Hz, 1H), 6.50 (dt, *J* = 17.0, 10.4 Hz, 1H), 6.43 (br d, *J* = 11.5 Hz, 1H), 6.27 (ddt, *J* = 12.3, 10.8, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 5.39 (ddt, *J* = 16.9, 2.0, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 5.34 (ddt, *J* = 16.9, 1.7, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 5.24 (ddt, *J* = 10.1, 2.1, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 5.19 (ddt, *J* = 10.0, 1.5, 0.7 Hz, 1H), 2.31 (s, 3H), 2.30 (s, 3H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 169.6, 169.5, 150.2, 149.7, 137.1, 135.2, 135.0, 133.1, 131.9, 131.1, 130.1, 129.9, 129.5, 127.5, 121.8, 121.5, 120.1, 117.9, 21.2 (2 x).

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 1498 (m), 1423 (m), 1250 (m), 1209 (s), 1136 (s), 885 (s), 854 (m), 758 (s).

HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M + H]⁺ Calcd for C₁₂H₁₃O₂⁺ 189.0910; Found 189.0909.

Isolated as a 1:2 mixture of E/Z isomers. 350 mg, 50.3% yield (3 mmol scale). Yellow oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.46 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.38 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 7.25 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 4H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.85 – 6.74 (m, 3H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 15.3 Hz, 1H), 6.51 (dt, *J* = 16.9, 10.5 Hz, 1H), 6.42 (d, *J* = 11.6 Hz, 2H), 6.33 (t, *J* = 11.3 Hz, 2H), 5.44 (br d, *J* = 16.1 Hz, 2H), 5.40 (br d, *J* = 16.4 Hz, 1H), 5.30 (br d, *J* = 10.2 Hz, 2H), 5.26 (br d, *J* = 9.6 Hz, 1H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 148.8, 148.4, 137.9, 137.8, 136.7, 132.5, 132.5, 131.7, 130.8, 130.7, 128.3, 128.0, 121.7, 121.3, 121.3, 119.4, 118.9 (q, *J* = 320.8 Hz).

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -72.84.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 1498 (m), 1423 (m), 1250 (m), 1209 (s), 1136 (s), 885 (s), 854 (m), 758 (s).

HRMS (APPI/LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M]⁺ Calcd for C₁₁H₉F₃O₃S⁺ 278.0219; Found 278.0218.

Isolated as a 2.9:1 mixture of Z/E isomers. 500 mg, 50.5% yield (5 mmol scale). Yellowish oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ [7.7-7.62 (m) + 7.54-7.47 (m) + 7.40-7.31 (m), 4H, Z + E], 6.94 (dq, *J* = 15.5, 2.6 Hz, 1/4H, *E*), 6.78 (dd, *J* = 15.4, 10.4 Hz, 1/4H, *E*), 6.69 (d, *J* = 11.5 Hz, 3/4H, *Z*), 6.56 (dtd, *J* = 16.8, 10.1, 1.0 Hz, 1H, Z + E), 6.39 (t, *J* = 11.3 Hz, 3/4H, *Z*), 5.40 (apparent d, *J* = 16.1 Hz, 1H, Z + E), 5.28 (apparent dt, *J* = 10.0, 0.8 Hz, 1/4H, *E*), 5.23 (apparent dt, *J* = 10.1, 2.0 Hz, 3/4H, *Z*).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 137.1, 136.2 (q, *J* = 1.8 Hz), 136.0 (q, *J* = 1.8 Hz), 133.5, 132.8, 132.8, 131.9 (br), 131.8, 131.4 (br), 128.7, 128.4 (q, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 2C), 127.3, 127.3, 127.1 (br), 126.9, 126.0 (q, *J* = 5.7 Hz), 125.7, 123.1, 123.0, 120.6, 119.5.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -59.43, -60.74.

IR (*v*_{max}, cm⁻¹) 1516 (m), 1313 (s), 1159 (s), 1115 (s), 1057 (m), 1036 (s), 1003 (m), 908 (m), 760 (s).

HRMS (LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M + H]⁺ Calcd for C₁₁H₁₀F₃⁺ 199.0729; Found 199.0728.

400 mg, 85%. Colorless oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.31 – 7.26 (m, 2H), 7.21 – 7.18 (m, 3H), 6.33 (dt, *J* = 17.0, 10.2 Hz, 1H), 5.96 (dd, *J* = 15.6, 10.2 Hz, 1H), 5.66 (d, *J* = 15.5 Hz, 1H), 5.12 (dd, *J* = 16.9, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 4.98 (dd, *J* = 10.1, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 2.58 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 1.61 – 1.53 (m, 2H), 1.39 – 1.34 (m, 2H), 1.02 (s, 6H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 145.3, 142.8, 137.9, 128.5, 128.4, 127.1, 125.8, 114.9, 42.9, 36.8, 36.2, 27.2, 26.8.

IR (*v*_{max}, cm⁻¹) 2926 (m), 2853 (m), 2359 (w), 2341 (w), 1617 (s), 1442 (w), 1364 (m), 1313 (m), 1005 (w), 699 (m).

HRMS (APPI/LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₂₂⁺ 214.1716; Found 214.1716.

4. Synthesis of the N-amidopyridinium tetrafluoroborates

Amidopyridinium salts **2a-b** were synthesized following a two-step procedure reported in the literature.^[16]

5. Synthesis of the copper sources and the chiral ligands

Synthesis of Cu(OTf)₂(H₂O)_x

Commercial white Cu(OTf)₂ was dissolved in water (the solution turned blue). The resulting blue liquid was evaporated under high vacuum and the resulting blue powder was lyophilized overnight.

Synthesis of the chiral ligand **L**

Ligand **L** was synthesized following a reported procedure. The spectroscopic data matched the reported data.^[17]

Complex **F** was synthesized following a reported procedure and after recrystallization in ethanol, **F** was obtained in 99% yield as white crystals.^[18]

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.22 (d, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 7.39 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 7.32 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 2H), 7.22 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 5.69 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 5.32

(t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H), 3.44 (dd, $J = 7.0, 18.3$ Hz 2H), 3.17 (d, $J = 18.2$ Hz, 2H), 1.78 – 1.62 (m, 4H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 166.8, 140.0, 138.9, 129.4, 128.3, 127.1, 125.1, 83.9, 77.4, 39.4, 20.1, 18.4.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 2360 (w), 2332 (w), 2104 (m), 1658 (s), 1429 (m), 1108 (s), 1002 (m), 761 (m), 728 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{CuN}_3\text{NaO}_2^+$ 468.0744; Found 468.0747.

6. Optimization of the reaction conditions

Racemic reaction

Entry	Cu salt	Result
1	Cu(acac) ₂	DP trace
2	Cu(OAc) ₂	DP trace
3	CuCl ₂	DP trace
4	Cu(OTf) ₂	DP trace
5	CuCl	DP 14%
6	CuOAc	DP trace
7	CuBr	DP <5%
8	CuI	DP trace
9	Cu(CH ₃ CN) ₄ ·BF ₄	DP <5%
10	CuTc	DP 10%

Table S1. Copper source screening

Entry	Solvent/1.0 mL	Result
1	DCM	DP 14%
2	CH ₃ CN	DP <5%
3	DCE	DP 8%
4	toluene	No DP
5	EtOAc	No DP
6	THF	No DP
7	DCM:DMA = 4:1	DP <5%

Table S2. Solvent screening

Asymmetric reaction

Figure S2. Ligand screening

Entry	Cu salt	Result
1	Cu(acac)_2	44% yield, 88% ee
2	Cu(OTf)_2 (hydrated)	44% yield, 92% ee
3	Cu(OTFA)_2	40% yield, 92% ee
4	Cu(OAc)_2	18% yield, 92% ee
5	CuCl	33% yield, 86% ee
6	$\text{Cu(CH}_3\text{CN)}_4\text{PF}_6$	15% yield, 92% ee
7	CuOAc	trace
8	CuTe	trace
9	$(\text{CuOTf})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$	28% yield
10	$\text{Cu(II) trifluoroacetylacetonate}$	30% yield

Table S3. Copper source screening

Entry	solvent	Result
1	DCM	44% yield, 92% ee
2	DCE	31% yield, 88% ee
3	CH_3CN	<5% yield
4	toluene	No DP
5	TBME	No DP
6	THF	trace
7	benzene	45% yield, 90% ee
8	PhF	44% yield, 90% ee
9	PhCF_3	27% yield
10	PhCl	42% yield
11	PhF_6	trace
12	CHCl_3 (degassed)	62% yield, 92% ee
13	TCE	48% yield, 40% ee

Table S4. Single solvent screening

Entry	mixed solvent	Result
1	DCM+C ₆ F ₆ (1:4)	30% yield
2	DCM+C ₆ F ₆ (4:1)	52% yield, 91% ee
3	DCM+PhF (1:1)	50% yield, 92% ee
4	DCM+PhCF ₃ (1:1)	53% yield, 92% ee
5	DCM/TFE (3:1)	No DP
6	DCM/Toluene (3:1)	42% yield
7	DCM/C ₆ F ₆ (2:1)	41% yield
8	DCM/C ₆ F ₆ (8:1)	55% yield

Table S5. Mixed solvent screening

Entry	⁻ CN source	Result
1	CuCN instead of Cu(OTf) ₂	21% yield
2	KCN	20% yield
3		21% yield

Table S6. Cyanide source screening

Entry	<i>fac</i> -Ir(ppy) ₃ (X mol%)	Result
1	1 mol%	52% yield, 91% ee
2	2 mol%	36% yield, 88% ee
3	0.5 mol%	39% yield, 90% ee

Table S7. Photocatalyst loading screening

Entry	X	Y	Z	Result
1	0.1 mmol	0.2 mmol	0.2 mmol	44% yield, 92% ee
2	0.2 mmol	0.1 mmol	0.2 mmol	messy
3	0.1 mmol	0.4 mmol	0.2 mmol	50% yield, 90% ee
4	0.1 mmol	0.2 mmol	0.4 mmol	30% yield
5	0.1 mmol	0.2 mmol	0.1 mmol	no reaction

Table S8. Reactant equivalents screening

7. General procedure for amidocyanation

A suspension of **1a** (0.1 mmol, 1.0 equiv), **2a** (0.12 mmol, 1.2 equiv), Cu(OTf)₂(H₂O)_x (0.02 mmol, 0.2 equiv), chiral ligand (0.024 mmol, 0.24 equiv), and *fac*-Ir(ppy)₃ (0.001 mmol, 0.01 equiv) in dry, degassed CHCl₃ (1.0 mL) was stirred in a dry tube at room temperature under N₂ for 10 min, then TMSCN (0.2 mmol, 2.0 equiv) was added to the above mixture. The reaction mixture was irradiated with 24W blue LEDs strips for 20 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under vacuum. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, eluting with petroleum ether/ethyl acetate to afford product **3a**.

8. Procedure for amidocyanation using F

A suspension of **1a** (0.1 mmol, 1.0 equiv), **2a** (0.12 mmol, 1.2 equiv), **F** (0.02 mmol, 0.2 equiv) and *fac*-Ir(ppy)₃ (0.001 mmol, 0.01 equiv) in dry, degassed CHCl₃ (1.0 mL) was stirred in a dry tube at room temperature under N₂ for 10 min, then TMSCN (0.2 mmol, 2.0 equiv) was added to the above mixture. The reaction mixture was irradiated with 24W blue LEDs strips for 20 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under vacuum. The residue was

purified by column chromatography on silica gel, eluting with petroleum ether/ethyl acetate to afford product **3a** in 51% yield and 94% ee.

9. Characterization data of compounds **3** and **5**

3a. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-phenylbut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

Run at 0 °C over 6 h. 18 mg, 66% yield. Yellow waxy oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40 – 7.28 (m, 5H), 6.78 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 6.02 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.80-3.72 (m, 1H), 3.55 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.37 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 135.6, 135.2, 128.9, 128.7, 126.8, 119.9, 119.2, 80.5, 43.3, 36.1, 28.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 2978 (w), 2156 (w), 1697 (s), 1514 (s), 1452 (w), 1367 (m), 1273 (m), 1252 (s), 1165 (s), 966 (m), 746 (m), 696 (m).

HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₂₀N₂NaO₂⁺ 295.1417; Found 295.1419.

[α]_D²² 31.7 (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃), 96% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.5% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. tR = 5.8 min (major), 6.8 min (minor).

3b. (*R,E*)-4-(4-((*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)-3-cyanobut-1-en-1-yl)phenyl acetate

16.3 mg, 49% yield. White waxy oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.38 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 7.07 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H), 6.76 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 5.97 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (br s, 1H), 3.76 (apparent q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.53 (dt, *J* = 13.9, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.37 (dt, *J* = 13.9, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 2.30 (s, 3H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 169.5, 155.8, 150.9, 134.1, 133.3, 127.8, 122.1, 120.2, 119.1, 80.5, 43.2, 36.1, 28.4, 21.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 1763 (m), 1705 (s), 1508 (s), 1367 (m), 1250 (m), 1194 (s), 1167 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_4^+$ 353.1472; Found 353.1469.

$[\alpha]^{22}_{\text{D}}$ 11.0 (c 0.8, CHCl_3), 92% ee.

SFC: IA column, 3.0% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_{R} = 2.9 min (major), 3.4 min (minor).

3c. (*R,E*)-4-(4-((*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)-3-cyanobut-1-en-1-yl)phenyl trifluoromethanesulfonate

21 mg, 50% yield. Yellow waxy oil.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.45 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.25 (d, J = 8.9 Hz, 2H), 6.78 (d, J = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 6.06 (dd, J = 15.9, 6.2 Hz, 1H), 4.98 (t, J = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 3.81-3.76 (m, 1H), 3.55 (dt, J = 14.0, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.41 (dt, J = 14.0, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.41 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 155.8, 149.4, 136.0, 133.0, 128.5, 122.4, 121.9, 118.8, 118.7 (q, J = 321.0 Hz), 80.6, 43.1, 36.3, 28.4.

^{19}F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl_3) δ -72.76.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2156 (w), 1701 (m), 1502 (m), 1423 (m), 1250 (m), 1209 (s), 1167 (m), 1138 (s), 885 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_5\text{S}^+$ 443.0859; Found 443.0857.

$[\alpha]^{22}_{\text{D}}$ 7.3 (c 1, CHCl_3), 82% ee.

SFC: IA column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_{R} = 1.6 min (major), 2.0 min (minor).

3d. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(4-fluorophenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

21.2 mg, 73% yield. White solid. M. p. = 75 - 78 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.35 (dd, J = 8.5, 5.4 Hz, 2H), 7.03 (t, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 6.74 (d, J = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 5.94 (dd, J = 15.9, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (br s, 1H), 3.75 (q, J = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.54 (dt, J = 14.0, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.38 (dt, J = 14.0, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 162.9 (d, J = 248.2 Hz), 155.8, 133.9, 131.8 (br), 128.4 (d, J = 8.2 Hz), 119.8, 119.1, 115.9 (d, J = 21.8 Hz), 80.5, 43.2, 36.1, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -112.93.

IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) 2978 (w), 2162 (w), 1701 (s), 1603 (w), 1508 (s), 1367 (m), 1250 (m), 1230 (s), 1161 (s), 968 (m), 854 (m), 814 (w).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉FN₂NaO₂⁺ 313.1323; Found 313.1328.

[α]²²_D 21.2 (c 0.6, CHCl₃), 96% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.5% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. tR = 4.5 min (major), 5.4 min (minor).

3e. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(4-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-cyanobut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

13 mg, 42% yield. White solid. M. p. = 112 - 114 °C

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.30 (s, 4H), 6.73 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 6.00 (dd, *J* = 16.0, 6.6, Hz, 1H), 5.00 (br s, 1H), 3.78-3.73 (m, 1H), 3.54 (dt, *J* = 14.6, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.38 (dt, *J* = 14.6, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 134.4, 134.1, 133.8, 129.1, 128.0, 120.7, 118.9, 80.5, 43.2, 36.2, 28.3.

IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) 2976 (m), 1701 (s), 1516 (s), 1367 (m), 1252 (s), 1165 (s), 1090 (m), 1012 (m), 968 (m), 864 (m), 802 (m), 717 (m).

HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉ClN₂NaO₂⁺ 329.1027; Found 329.1024.

[α]²²_D 37.0 (c 0.5, CHCl₃), 89% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.5% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. tR = 10.3 min (major), 12.2 min (minor).

3f. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(4-(4-bromophenyl)-2-cyanobut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

18.3 mg, 52% yield. White solid. M. p. = 96 - 98 °C

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.46 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.72 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 6.02 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 4.98 (br s, 1H), 3.75 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.54 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.39 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 134.5, 133.9, 132.0, 128.3, 122.6, 120.8, 119.0, 80.6, 43.1, 36.2, 28.4.

IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) 1695 (s), 1518 (s), 1388 (s), 1365 (s), 1275 (s), 1252 (s), 1167 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉BrN₂NaO₂⁺ 373.0522; Found 373.0521
[α]_D²² 28.3 (c 0.5, CHCl₃), 90% ee.

SFC: IF column, 4% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 4.0 min (major), 5.6 min (minor).

3g. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(4-iodophenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

17 mg, 43% yield. White solid. M. p. = 118 – 121°C

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.66 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 6.70 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 6.03 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (t, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.75 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.54 (dt, *J* = 13.9, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.38 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 138.0, 135.1, 134.0, 128.5, 120.9, 118.9, 94.2, 80.6, 43.1, 36.2, 28.4.

IR (ν_{max}, cm⁻¹) 3344 (m), 2031 (m), 1689 (s), 1527 (s), 1289 (m), 1253 (m), 1168 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉IN₂NaO₂⁺ 421.0383; Found 421.0383
[α]_D²² 16.5 (c 0.7, CHCl₃), 91% ee.

SFC: ID column, 5% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 2.6 min (major), 3.3 min (minor).

3h. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

23 mg, 66% yield. Yellow solid. M. p. = 113 – 115 °C.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.59 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.47 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 6.82 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 6.13 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.2 Hz, 1H), 5.03 (br s, 1H), 3.80 (q, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.56 (dt, *J* = 14.2, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.42 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 138.9, 133.6, 130.4 (q, *J* = 32.5 Hz), 127.0, 125.8 (q, *J* = 3.8 Hz), 124.1 (q, *J* = 272.6 Hz), 122.8, 118.8, 80.6, 43.1, 36.2, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -62.66.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 2937 (w), 2276 (w), 1685 (s), 1525 (s), 1329 (s), 1294 (m), 1163 (s), 1115 (s), 1068 (m), 949 (m), 862 (m), 758 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₇H₁₉F₃N₂NaO₂⁺ 363.1291; Found 363.1293.

[α]¹⁹_D 24.8 (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃), 89% ee.

SFC: IF column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 2 mL/min. *t*_R = 1.6 min (major), 2.2 min (minor).

3i. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(3-methoxyphenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

17.1 mg, 57% yield. Yellowish oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.27 – 7.23 (m, 1H), 6.97 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 6.90 (s, 1H), 6.85 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 2.6 Hz, 1H), 6.75 (d, *J* = 15.8 Hz, 1H), 6.01 (dd, *J* = 15.8, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 5.01 (s, 1H), 3.82 (s, 3H), 3.79 – 3.72 (m, 1H), 3.55 (dt, *J* = 14.2, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.37 (dt, *J* = 14.2, 7.3 Hz, 1H), 1.44 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 160.0, 155.8, 136.9, 135.1, 129.9, 120.3, 119.4, 119.1, 114.4, 112.1, 80.5, 55.4, 43.3, 36.1, 28.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 2979 (m), 2158 (s), 1705 (s), 1595 (m), 1514 (s), 1365 (m), 1271 (s), 1163 (s), 1047 (m), 966 (m), 806 (m), 719 (s).

HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₇H₂₂N₂NaO₃⁺ 325.1523; Found 325.1524.

[α]²²_D 35.1 (*c* 1.0, CH₂Cl₂), 91% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.5% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. *t*_R = 7.7 min (major), 8.8 min (minor).

3j. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(4-(3-chlorophenyl)-2-cyanobut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

16 mg, 52% yield. Yellow oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.37 (s, 1H), 7.28 – 7.22 (m, 3H), 6.73 (br d, *J* = 15.8 Hz, 1H), 6.04 (dd, *J* = 15.8, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (br s, 1H), 3.80-3.71 (m, 1H), 3.54 (apparent dt, *J* = 14.2, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 3.39 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 137.4, 134.9, 133.8, 130.1, 128.6, 126.7, 125.1, 121.6, 118.9, 80.6, 43.1, 36.1, 28.4.

IR (*v*_{max}, cm⁻¹) 2978 (w), 2933 (w), 1701 (s), 1514 (s), 1392 (m), 1367 (m), 1252 (s), 1167 (s), 962 (m), 879 (m), 779 (m), 715 (m).

HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉ClN₂NaO₂⁺ 329.1027; Found 329.1028.

[α]²¹_D 32.5 (*c* 0.7, CHCl₃), 89% ee.

SFC: IF column, 6.0% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 2 mL/min. *t*_R = 1.7 min (major), 2.6 min (minor).

3k. methyl (*R,E*)-3-(4-((*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)amino)-3-cyanobut-1-en-1-yl)benzoate

18 mg, 54% yield. White solid. M. p. = 87 – 88 °C.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.06 (t, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (dt, *J* = 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.42 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 6.82 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 6.11 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (br s, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 3.79 (q, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 3.56 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.40 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 166.9, 155.8, 135.9, 134.2, 131.2, 130.9, 129.6, 129.0, 127.7, 121.4, 118.9, 80.6, 52.4, 43.2, 36.1, 28.4.

IR (*v*_{max}, cm⁻¹) 1718 (m), 1514 (m), 1288 (m), 1275 (m), 1261 (m), 1205 (m), 1169 (m), 758 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₈H₂₂N₂NaO₄⁺ 353.1472; Found 353.1482.

[α]²²_D 13.1 (*c* 0.6, CHCl₃), 93% ee.

SFC: OD-H column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. *t*_R = 11.1 min (major), 12.5 min (minor).

3l. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(*o*-tolyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

19 mg, 66% yield. White solid. M. p. = 69 – 71 °C.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.42 – 7.35 (m, 1H), 7.23 – 7.14 (m, 3H), 6.99 (d, *J* = 15.7 Hz, 1H), 5.90 (dd, *J* = 15.7, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (s, 1H), 3.78 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.55 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.40 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 2.36 (s, 3H), 1.44 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 135.9, 134.8, 133.3, 130.6, 128.5, 126.4, 126.0, 121.3, 119.2, 80.5, 43.3, 36.3, 28.4, 19.9.

IR (*v*_{max}, cm⁻¹) 2976 (w), 2154 (w), 1701 (s), 1514 (s), 1458 (m), 1367 (m), 1271 (m), 1252 (s), 1167 (s), 966 (m), 868 (w), 748 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₇H₂₂N₂NaO₂⁺ 309.1573; Found 309.1574.

[α]²¹_D 40.5 (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃), 90% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.0% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. tR = 6.9 min (major), 7.9 min (minor).

3m. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(2-fluorophenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

20 mg, 69% yield. Yellow waxy oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.40 (td, *J* = 7.6, 1.8 Hz, 1H), 7.29 – 7.23 (m, 1H), 7.14 – 7.03 (m, 2H), 6.89 (d, *J* = 16.0 Hz, 1H), 6.14 (dd, *J* = 16.0, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (br s, 1H), 3.78 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.55 (dt, *J* = 13.9, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.40 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 160.4 (d, *J* = 250.8 Hz), 155.8, 130.0 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz), 128.2 (d, *J* = 3.7 Hz, 2C), 124.4 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz), 123.4 (d, *J* = 11.9 Hz), 122.9 (d, *J* = 6.2 Hz), 119.0, 116.1 (d, *J* = 22.0 Hz), 80.5, 43.2, 36.5, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -116.8.

IR (*v*_{max}, cm⁻¹) 1699 (s), 1512 (s), 1491 (s), 1456 (m), 1367 (m), 1252 (s), 1167 (s), 968 (m), 758 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉FN₂NaO₂⁺ 313.1323; Found 313.1324.

[α]²²_D 27.6 (*c* 0.6, CHCl₃), 93% ee.

SFC: IF column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 2 mL/min. tR = 2.0 min (major), 3.7 min (minor).

3n. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(4-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-cyanobut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

12.5 mg, 41% yield. Yellow waxy oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.49 – 7.46 (m, 1H), 7.39 – 7.34 (m, 1H), 7.25 – 7.21 (m, 2H), 7.14 (dd, *J* = 15.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 6.01 (dd, *J* = 15.8, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 5.01 (br s, 1H), 3.79 (q, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.55 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.43 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 133.9, 133.5, 131.7, 130.0, 129.6, 127.3, 127.1, 123.0, 118.9, 80.6, 43.1, 36.3, 28.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 1697 (s), 1516 (s), 1367 (m), 1271 (m), 1252 (s), 1165 (s), 1036 (m), 966 (m), 752 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉ClN₂NaO₂⁺ 329.1027; Found 329.1028.

[α]²⁵_D 19.3 (*c* 0.3, CHCl₃), 88% ee.

SFC: IF column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 2 mL/min. tR = 2.6 min (major), 5.9 min (minor).

3o. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(4-(2-bromophenyl)-2-cyanobut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

14.5 mg, 41% yield. Yellow oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.56 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.46 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 7.28 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.15 (td, *J* = 7.6, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.10 (d, *J* = 16.8 Hz, 1H), 5.96 (dd, *J* = 15.8, 6.7 Hz, 1H), 5.00 (br s, 1H), 3.78 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.55 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.44 (dt, *J* = 13.9, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 135.7, 134.3, 133.2, 129.9, 127.8, 127.5, 123.9, 123.2, 118.9, 80.6, 43.0, 36.2, 28.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 1700 (s), 1510 (s), 1366 (m), 1271 (m), 1252 (s), 1164 (s), 1024 (m), 963 (m), 762 (m), 751 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₁₉BrN₂NaO₂⁺ 373.0522; Found 373.0519.

$[\alpha]^{22}_{\text{D}}$ 22.7 (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃), 93% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.5% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. *t*_R = 9.2 min (major), 11.0 min (minor).

3p. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(2-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

18.0 mg, 53% yield. Yellow oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.65 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.57 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.52 (t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.40 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 15.7 Hz, 1H), 5.99 (dd, *J* = 15.6, 6.8 Hz, 1H), 4.97 (br s, 1H), 3.77 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.56-3.43 (m, 2H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 134.8, 132.2, 131.7, 128.3, 128.0, 127.9 (*q*, *J* = 30.0 Hz), 126.0 (*q*, *J* = 5.7 Hz), 124.7, 124.2 (*q*, *J* = 274.0 Hz), 118.7, 80.6, 42.9, 36.2, 28.4.

¹⁹F NMR (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ -59.42.

IR (ν_{max} , cm⁻¹) 1701 (s), 1520 (m), 1365 (s), 1313 (s), 1252 (m), 1161 (s), 1119 (s), 1036 (s), 768 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₇H₁₉F₃N₂NaO₂⁺ 363.1291; Found 363.1294.

$[\alpha]^{22}_{\text{D}}$ 27.6 (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃), 96% ee.

SFC: OD-H column, 2.0% MeOH in supercritical CO₂ as eluent, 4 mL/min. *t*_R = 4.0 min (minor), 5.0 min (major).

3q. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

22 mg, 66% yield. Yellow oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.71 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 6.52 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 2H), 6.41 (t, *J* = 2.3 Hz, 1H), 6.00 (dd, *J* = 15.8, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 4.98 (br s, 1H), 3.80 (s, 6H), 3.76 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.54 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.36 (dt, *J* = 14.1, 7.0 Hz, 1H), 1.44 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 161.1, 155.7, 137.5, 135.2, 120.5, 119.1, 104.8, 100.9, 80.5, 55.5, 43.3, 36.0, 28.4.

IR (ν_{max} , cm⁻¹) 1698 (m), 1592 (s), 1520 (m), 1457 (m), 1252 (m), 1204 (m), 1153 (s), 1061 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{16}H_{22}N_4NaO_2^+$ 325.1635; Found 325.1637.

$[\alpha]^{21}_D$ 11.7 (c 0.4, $CHCl_3$), 92% ee.

SFC: IA column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 2.4 min (minor), 2.7 min (major).

3r. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-mesitylbut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

17 mg, 54% yield. White solid. M.p = 67 – 68 °C.

1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 6.87 (s, 2H), 6.77 (d, J = 16.1 Hz, 1H), 5.53 (dd, J = 16.1, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 5.01 (br s, 1H), 3.80 (q, J = 6.9 Hz, 1H), 3.56 (dt, J = 13.8, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.38 (dt, J = 14.0, 6.9 Hz, 1H), 2.27 (s, 3H), 2.25 (s, 6H), 1.46 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 155.7, 137.2, 135.9, 133.5, 132.3, 128.8, 124.9, 119.2, 80.5, 43.3, 36.2, 28.4, 21.1, 20.9.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 2979 (m), 2025 (m), 1709 (s), 1514 (s), 1452 (m), 1365 (m), 1252 (s), 1167 (s), 972 (m), 847 (m), 739 (m), 683 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{19}H_{26}N_2NaO_2^+$ 337.1886; Found 337.1893.

$[\alpha]^{21}_D$ 35.8 (c 1.0, CH_2Cl_2), 87% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 0.5% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 4 mL/min. t_R = 5.8 min (major), 6.7 min (minor).

3s. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-phenylpent-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

10.1 mg, 35% yield. White waxy oil.

1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.39 – 7.28 (m, 5H), 5.58 (d, J = 9.8 Hz, 1H), 5.00 (br s, 1H), 3.93 (q, J = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 3.46 (dt, J = 14.0, 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.37 (dt, J = 14.1, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 2.14 (d, J = 1.4 Hz, 3H), 1.46 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 155.8, 142.5, 141.9, 128.6, 128.2, 126.1, 119.9, 118.1, 80.5, 43.1, 32.0, 28.5, 16.7.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 2528 (m), 2023 (m), 1703 (m), 1518 (m), 1275 (m), 1250 (m), 1167 (m), 758 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{17}H_{22}N_2NaO_2^+$ 309.1573; Found 309.1570.

$[\alpha]^{21}_D$ 26.9 (c 0.5, $CHCl_3$), 77% ee.

SFC: IF column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 2.1 min (major), 2.8 min (minor).

3t. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-3-methyl-4-phenylbut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

18.6 mg, 65% yield. Yellow oil.

1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.38 – 7.32 (m, 2H), 7.29 – 7.23 (m, 3H), 6.63 (s, 1H), 4.96 (br s, 1H), 3.66-3.56 (m, 2H), 3.42 (dt, J = 13.9, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 1.99 (d, J = 1.4 Hz, 3H), 1.44 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 155.8, 136.5, 130.8, 129.2, 129.1, 128.4, 127.4, 119.4, 80.5, 42.4, 42.1, 28.4, 16.2.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 2156 (s), 1707 (s), 1523 (s), 1508 (s), 1367 (s), 1265 (s), 1252 (s), 1165 (s), 700 (s).

HRMS (nanochip-ESI/LTQ-Orbitrap) m/z : $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{17}H_{22}N_2NaO_2^+$ 309.1573; Found 309.1577.

$[\alpha]^{21}_D$ 6.9 (c 0.6, $CHCl_3$), 97% ee.

SFC: OJ-H column, 1.5% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 4 mL/min. t_R = 4.4 min (major), 5.3 min (minor).

3u. *tert*-butyl (*R*)-(2-cyano-2-(3,4-dihydronaphthalen-2-yl)ethyl)carbamate

13.7 mg, 46% yield. White solid. M.p. = 68 – 71 °C

1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.22 – 7.15 (m, 2H), 7.13-7.10 (m, 1H), 7.09 – 7.03 (m, 1H), 6.59 (s, 1H), 4.96 (br s, 1H), 3.69 (t, J = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.60 (dt, J = 13.8, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.37 (ddd, J = 14.0, 8.0, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 2.87 (t, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 2.45 (dt, J = 16.7, 8.1 Hz, 1H), 2.32 (dt, J = 16.7, 8.4 Hz, 1H), 1.42 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 155.7, 134.6, 133.0, 131.2, 128.0, 127.6, 127.5, 126.9, 126.7, 119.1, 80.5, 42.1, 40.0, 28.4, 27.9, 25.5.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 2528 (s), 2164 (s), 2139 (s), 1701m (s), 1506 (s), 1254 (s), 1167 (s)

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{18}H_{22}N_2NaO_2^+$ 321.1573; Found 321.1569

$[\alpha]^{21}_D$ 14.8 (c 0.5, $CHCl_3$), 91% ee.

SFC: IF column, 3% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 3.2 min (major), 5.4 min (minor).

3v. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-4-(thiophen-3-yl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

12 mg, 43% yield. Yellow oil.

1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.30 (dd, J = 5.0, 3.0 Hz, 1H), 7.23 (dd, J = 3.0, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.18 (dd, J = 5.0, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 6.78 (d, J = 15.8 Hz, 1H), 5.87 (dd, J = 15.8, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 4.97 (br s, 1H), 3.73 (q, J = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.53 (dt, J = 13.9, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.35 (dt, J = 14.0, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.43 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 155.7, 138.1, 129.3, 126.7, 124.9, 123.9, 119.6, 119.1, 80.5, 43.3, 36.0, 28.4.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 1699 (s), 1525 (s), 1506 (s), 1365 (s), 1267 (s), 1250 (s), 1163 (s), 960 (s), 775 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + Na]^+$ Calcd for $C_{14}H_{18}N_2NaO_2S^+$ 301.0981; Found 301.0981.

$[\alpha]^{21}_D$ 30.4 (c 0.4, $CHCl_3$), 93% ee.

SFC: IF column, 6% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 1.9 min (major), 3.0 min (minor).

3w. (*R,E*)-2-(((2-oxo-2-phenyl-1H-imidazol-1-yl)amino)methyl)-4-phenylbut-3-enenitrile

14 mg, 49% yield. Yellow oil.

1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 7.40 – 7.27 (m, 10H), 6.78 (d, J = 15.8 Hz, 1H), 6.02 (dd, J = 15.9, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 5.22 (br s, 1H), 5.12 (q, J = 8.5 Hz, 2H), 5.14 (d, J = 12.0 Hz, 1H), 5.09 (d, J = 12.1 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (q, J = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.62 (dt, J = 14.0, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.46 (dt, J = 14.0, 7.0 Hz, 1H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 156.4, 136.1, 135.5, 135.4, 128.9, 128.7 (2C), 128.5, 128.3, 126.8, 119.6, 118.9, 67.4, 43.6, 36.0.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2158 (s), 2021 (s), 1712 (s), 1539 (s), 1244 (s), 968 (s), 746 (s), 690 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_2^+$ 329.1260; Found 329.1259.

$[\alpha]_D^{21}$ 15.7 (c 0.6, CHCl_3), 93% ee.

SFC: IF column, 9% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 3.3 min (major), 3.9 min (minor).

3x. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-5,5-dimethylhex-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

14 mg, 49% yield. Yellow oil.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.89 (d, J = 15.6 Hz, 1H), 5.20 (dd, J = 15.6, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 4.92 (br s, 1H), 3.51 (q, J = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.43 (dt, J = 13.9, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 3.24 (dt, J = 13.9, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 1.44 (s, 9H), 1.02 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 155.7, 147.8, 119.8, 115.8, 80.3, 43.3, 35.8, 33.5, 29.3, 28.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2962 (m), 1705 (s), 1641 (m), 1523 (s), 1365 (m), 1271 (m), 1250 (s), 1169 (s), 717 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{H}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^+$ 253.1911; Found 253.1914.

3x'. (*R,E*)-*N*-(2-cyano-5,5-dimethylhex-3-en-1-yl)-4-methylbenzenesulfonamide 15 mg, 95% yield.

Yellow oil.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.76 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 2H), 7.34 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.87 (dd, J = 15.6, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 5.14 (dd, J = 15.6, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 4.82 (br s, 1H), 3.41 (dtd, J = 7.7, 6.4, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 3.25-3.13 (m, 2H), 2.44 (s, 3H), 1.01 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 148.9, 144.2, 136.9, 130.1, 127.2, 118.8, 115.1, 45.3, 35.8, 33.6, 29.3, 21.7.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2956 (m), 2362 (m), 1458 (w), 1331 (m), 1159 (s), 1092 (m), 974 (w), 816 (m), 758 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_2\text{S}^+$ 329.1294; Found 329.1302

$[\alpha]_D^{21}$ 122.3 (c 1.0, CHCl_3), 62% ee.

SFC: IF column, 9% MeOH in supercritical CO_2 as eluent, 2 mL/min. t_R = 1.3 min (minor), 2.0 min (major).

3y. *tert*-butyl (*R,E*)-(2-cyano-5,5-dimethyl-8-phenyloct-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

12 mg, 34% yield. Yellow oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.30 – 7.14 (m, 5H), 5.80 (dd, *J* = 15.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 5.15 (dd, *J* = 15.7, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 4.90 (t, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 3.52 (q, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 3.42 (dt, *J* = 12.7, 6.4 Hz, 1H), 3.21 (ddd, *J* = 14.1, 8.2, 6.1 Hz, 1H), 2.56 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 1.57 – 1.47 (m, 2H), 1.44 (s, 9H), 1.36 – 1.30 (m, 2H), 0.98 (s, 3H), 0.97 (s, 3H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.7, 146.6, 142.5, 128.5, 128.5, 125.9, 119.74, 117.01, 80.3, 43.4, 42.3, 36.6, 36.4, 35.8, 28.4, 27.1, 26.9, 26.6.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 2934 (m), 1714 (s), 1511 (s), 1366 (s), 1271 (m), 1252 (s), 1169 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₂₂H₃₂N₂NaO₂⁺ 379.2356; Found 379.2364.

[α]_D²² 19.1 (*c* 0.5, CHCl₃), 50% ee.

HPLC: IA column, 1% *i*PrOH in hexane as eluent, 0.5 mL/min. *t*R = 14.5 min (minor), 15.8 min (major).

3z. *tert*-butyl ((*R,E*)-2-cyano-4-((8*R*,9*S*,13*S*,14*S*)-13-methyl-17-oxo-7,8,9,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-decahydro-6*H*-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-3-yl)but-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

20 mg, 45% yield, d.r. > 20:1 Yellow waxy oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.27 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 1H), 7.17 (dd, *J* = 8.1, 2.0 Hz, 1H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 6.72 (d, *J* = 15.9 Hz, 1H), 5.96 (dd, *J* = 15.9, 6.5 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 3.78 – 3.70 (m, 1H), 3.54 (dt, *J* = 13.0, 6.3 Hz, 1H), 3.35 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 2.91 (dd, *J* = 9.0, 4.3 Hz, 2H), 2.51 (dd, *J* = 18.7, 8.6 Hz, 1H), 2.46-2.39 (m, 1H), 2.30 (td, *J* = 10.6, 4.2 Hz, 1H), 2.20 – 1.94 (m, 4H), 1.69 – 1.47 (m, 6H), 1.44 (s, 9H), 0.91 (s, 3H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 220.9, 155.8, 140.5, 137.0, 135.0, 133.2, 127.4, 125.9, 124.2, 119.2, 80.5, 50.6, 48.1, 44.6, 43.3, 38.2, 36.1, 36.0, 31.7, 29.5, 28.42, 28.37, 26.5, 25.8, 21.7, 14.0.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2930 (m), 2359 (w), 2341 (w), 1735 (s), 1711 (s), 1501 (m), 1366 (m), 1269 (m), 1252 (m), 1167 (s), 1084 (w), 1052 (w), 1008 (w), 967 (m), 912 (m), 731 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_3^+$ 471.2618; Found 471.2616.

3aa. *tert*-butyl (*E*)-(4-cyanobut-2-en-1-yl)carbamate

9.7 mg, 49% yield. White solid. M. p. = 92 – 93 °C.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 5.86 (dtt, $J = 14.9, 5.6, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 5.53 (dtt, $J = 15.2, 5.4, 1.7$ Hz, 1H), 4.63 (br s, 1H), 3.77 (br t, $J = 6.3$ Hz, 2H), 3.12-3.09 (m, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 155.8, 132.6, 119.1, 117.4, 79.8, 41.7, 28.5, 20.3.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 3321 (s), 1672 (s), 1527 (s), 1365 (m), 1250 (s), 1163 (s), 1047 (m), 966 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_2^+$ 219.1104; Found 219.1106.

3ab. *tert*-butyl (*E*)-(4-cyano-2,3-dimethylbut-2-en-1-yl)carbamate

Isolated as an unseparable 1:10 *cis*:*trans* mixture of alkenes. 14.7 mg, 66% yield. Yellow oil.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 4.49 (br s, 1H), 3.77 (d, $J = 5.9$ Hz, 2H), 3.09 (s, 2H), 1.89 (s, 3H), 1.74 (s, 3H), 1.44 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 156.1, 131.7, 121.5, 117.8, 79.7, 43.1, 28.5, 22.9, 18.3, 17.0.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 1695 (s), 1520 (s), 1456 (m), 1365 (s), 1275 (s), 1246 (s), 1165 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[M + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_2^+$ 247.1417; Found 247.1420.

5. *tert*-butyl ((*S,2E,4E*)-7-cyano-7-phenylhepta-2,4-dien-1-yl)carbamate

10 mg, 32% yield. Yellow waxy oil.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.41 – 7.30 (m, 5H), 6.17 – 6.06 (m, 2H), 5.68-5.57 (m, 2H), 4.55 (apparent s, 1H), 3.83 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.76 (t, $J = 5.3$ Hz, 2H), 2.66 (td, $J = 7.1, 3.7$ Hz, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 155.8, 135.3, 133.8, 130.8, 130.4, 129.3, 128.4, 127.5, 127.4, 120.4, 79.6, 42.4, 39.0, 38.0, 28.5.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm^{-1}) 2360 (s), 2341 (s), 1700 (s), 1508 (m), 1367 (m), 1272 (m), 1250 (m), 1167 (s), 700 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_2^+$ 335.1730; Found 335.1730.

$[\alpha]^{22}_{\text{D}}$ -12.8 (c 0.5, CHCl_3), 66% ee.

HPLC: IA column, 1% iPrOH in hexane as eluent, 0.5 mL/min. t_{R} = 18.0 (minor), 19.84 min (major).

10. Gram-scale reaction

A suspension of **1a** (3.1 mmol, 1.0 equiv), **2a** (3.7 mmol, 1.2 equiv), $\text{Cu(OTf)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_x$ (0.62 mmol, 0.2 equiv), chiral ligand (0.74 mmol, 0.24 equiv), and fac-Ir(ppy)_3 (0.046 mmol, 0.015 equiv) in CHCl_3 (31.0 mL) was stirred in a dry 100 mL balloon flask at room temperature under N_2 for 10 min, then TMSCN (6.2 mmol, 2.0 equiv) was added to the above mixture. The reaction mixture was irradiated with two Kessil blue LEDs, A160 WE, 40 W, for 20 h. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under vacuum. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, eluting with petroleum ether/ethyl acetate to afford product **3a** in 62% isolated yield and 94% ee.

11. Post-functionalizations

Amidocyanide **6** was obtained via palladium catalyzed hydrogenation of compound **3a**.

To a solution of **3a** (17 mg, 0.06 mmol, 1 equiv) in a 3:1 mixture of AcOEt:EtOH (2 mL) was added Pd/C (10%) (0.66 mg, 0.006 mmol, 0.1 equiv). The mixture was stirred for 24 h under H₂ atmosphere (1 atm), filtered over Celite and finally concentrated under high vacuum.

Diamine **8** was obtained via CN reduction of compound **6**, followed by Cbz protection of the resulting free amine.

To a solution of **6** (24.1 mg, 87.8 μmol, 1.0 equiv) in diethyl ether (1 mL) was added lithium aluminium hydride (12.5 mg, 331 μmol, 3.76 equiv) and the solution was stirred at rt for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled down to 0 °C, followed by addition of Rochelle salt and vigorous stirring for 3 h. The biphasic mixture was diluted with NaOH (10%) and AcOEt. The organic phase was separated, and the aqueous phase was extracted with AcOEt (2 times). The combined organic phases were dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated under reduced pressure to provide a crude yellow oil.

The residue was transferred to a flame-dried balloon, followed by addition of potassium carbonate (12.1 mg, 87.8 μmol, 1 equiv) and benzyl chloroformate (11.9 μL, 83.4 μmol, 0.95 equiv). The system was purged with argon and THF (6 mL) was added. The resulting mixture was left to stir for 12 h at rt and diluted with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃. The organic phase was separated, and the aqueous phase was extracted with AcOEt (2 times). The combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated under reduced pressure to provide a residue, which was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (20% AcOEt in pentane) to afford 25 mg of pure diamine **8** in 69% yield over 2 steps.

Carboxylic acid **7** was obtained via hydrolysis and Boc deprotection of compound **6**.

A stirred solution of **6** (30 mg, 0.11 mmol, 1.0 equiv) in HCl (6M) (1.4 mL) was heated to reflux for 12 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude compound was recrystallized from methanol to yield 22.5 mg (90%) of carboxylic acid **7**.

12. Characterization data of post-functionalized compounds

6. *tert*-butyl (*R*)-(2-cyano-4-phenylbutyl)carbamate

17.5 mg, 99.8% yield. Colorless oil.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.39 – 7.23 (m, 5H), 5.00 (br s, 1H), 3.48 (dt, *J* = 14.0, 6.6 Hz, 1H), 3.32 (dt, *J* = 13.7, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 2.96 (dt, *J* = 14.5, 7.1 Hz, 1H), 2.90 – 2.75 (m, 2H), 2.00 – 1.90 (m, 2H), 1.50 (s, 9H).

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 155.8, 140.0, 128.8, 128.5, 126.6, 120.9, 80.4, 42.2, 33.2, 32.8, 31.3, 28.4.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 1695 (s), 1512 (m), 1454 (m), 1365 (m), 1273 (m), 1250 (s), 1165 (s), 756 (m), 700 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: [M + Na]⁺ Calcd for C₁₆H₂₂N₂NaO₂⁺ 297.1573; Found 297.1575.

7. (*R,E*)-2-((chloro-λ⁵-azaneyl)methyl)-4-phenylbut-3-enoic acid

22.5 mg, 90% yield. White powder

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.31 – 7.14 (m, 5H), 3.21 (t, *J* = 10.9 Hz, 1H), 3.14-3.03 (m, 1H), 2.81 – 2.65 (m, 3H), 2.06 (dt, *J* = 15.0, 7.3 Hz, 1H), 1.96-1.83 (m, 1H).

¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 176.1, 142.2, 129.6, 129.5, 127.3, 43.5, 41.4, 33.8, 32.8.

IR ($\nu_{\max}$, cm⁻¹) 3026 (s), 2953 (s), 2359 (s), 2341 (s), 1706 (s), 1496 (s), 1456 (s), 1409 (s), 1237 (m), 699 (s).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) *m/z*: M⁺ Calcd for C₁₁H₁₆NO₂⁺ 194.1176; Found 194.1175.

8. *tert*-butyl (*S,E*)-2-(((2-oxo-2-phenyl-1 λ^2 -ethyl)amino)methyl)-4-phenylbut-3-en-1-yl)carbamate

25 mg, 69% yield, yellow oil.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.38 – 7.24 (m, 7H), 7.21 – 7.15 (m, 3H), 5.51 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 1H), 5.13 (d, $J = 12.2$ Hz, 1H), 5.09 (d, $J = 12.2$ Hz, 1H), 4.97 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 1H), 3.33 – 3.18 (m, 2H), 3.16 – 3.00 (m, 2H), 2.70 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H), 1.70-1.60 (m, 1H), 1.58 – 1.49 (m, 2H), 1.44 (s, 9H).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 157.2, 156.9, 142.2, 136.8, 128.6, 128.5, 128.5, 128.2, 126.0, 79.5, 66.8, 41.3, 40.8, 39.6, 33.3, 31.5, 28.5.

IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 3349 (w), 2928 (w), 2359 (s), 2342 (s), 1692 (s), 1517 (s), 1456 (m), 1366 (m), 1251 (m), 1167 (m).

HRMS (ESI/QTOF) m/z : $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ Calcd for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_4^+$ 435.2254; Found 435.2251.

$[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{22}$ -0.2 (c 1.8, CHCl_3), 90% ee.

HPLC: IA column, 5% *i*PrOH in hexane as eluent, 0.5 mL/min. $t_{\text{R}} = 12.3$ min (minor), 13.2 min (major).

13. Mechanism study

Light ON/OFF experiment

Procedure: The reaction of **1a** and **2a** was run following the standard procedure. The light was sequentially turned ON for 120 min and OFF for 120 min over 10 hrs. The yields were measured based on the $^1\text{H NMR}$ using 1,3,5-trimethoxybenzene as an internal standard.

Figure S3. Light ON/OFF experiment.

Discussion: Figure S1 showed that the formation of the desired product only occurred during constant irradiation with the blue LEDs. This result may indicate that radical chain process is not possible.

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15. Copies of NMR Spectra

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¹H, 400 MHz, CDCl₃

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137.13
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¹³C, 100 MHz, CDCl₃

^{19}F , 376 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

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136.03
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133.47
132.81
132.77
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128.73
128.43
128.39
128.37
128.35
127.34
127.26
127.06
126.07
126.01
125.96
125.90
125.67
123.13
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^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

-59.43
-60.74

^{19}F , 376 MHz, CDCl_3

¹³C, 100 MHz, CDCl₃

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

^{19}F , 376 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{19}F , 376 MHz, CDCl_3

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^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

^{13}C , 100 MHz, CDCl_3

^1H , 400 MHz, CDCl_3

16. Copies of HPLC/SFC Spectra

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
1.5p methanol	10	MeOH	OJ-H	DFO073	12D	29.8	4	1.5	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	98.1437	17605.439 1	5.77 min	804.6416	0
2	1.8563	332.9903	6.82 min	16.4769	0

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	6.06 min	10490.506	50.3123
2	7.1 min	10360.2634	49.6877

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-26 17:19:42+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IA 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IA
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.934	MM m	0.59	1225.18	108.13	96.21	
3.431	MM m	0.44	48.23	4.17	3.79	
Sum			1273.41			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-26 15:35:33+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-F9
Acq. method: Run IA 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IA
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.964	MM m	0.52	256.16	23.22	50.07	
3.457	MM m	0.56	255.48	20.55	49.93	
Sum			511.65			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-27 10:59:30+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IA 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IA
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1F,Sig=240,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.584	MM m	0.41	282.46	32.26	91.15	
1.978	MM m	0.40	27.41	2.62	8.85	
Sum			309.87			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-23 13:36:11+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-C1
Acq. method: Run IA 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IA
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1A,Sig=270,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.679	MM m	0.42	287.61	34.88	50.48	
2.086	MM m	0.58	282.10	27.17	49.52	
Sum			569.70			

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
1.5p methanol	10	MeOH	OJ-H	DFO095	12D	30	4	1.5	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	97.7798	6668.6532	4.52 min	307.7817	0
2	2.2202	151.4187	5.41 min	7.9646	0

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	5.53 min	9673.4853	50.3769
2	6.13 min	9528.7475	49.6231

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	10.31 min	16800.0474	94.4436
2	12.18 min	988.4051	5.5564

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	10.05 min	11851.0143	50.3685
2	11.82 min	11677.6275	49.6315

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-27 14:52:42+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 4% MeOH 10 minutes,amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration,pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1A,Sig=270,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
3.961	MM m	0.58	865.70	93.02	95.19	
5.566	MM m	0.56	43.74	3.33	4.81	
		Sum	909.43			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-04 13:15:13+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 4% MeOH 10 minutes,amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration,pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
3.930	MM m	0.63	1193.04	129.76	50.29	
5.405	MM m	0.73	1179.07	86.66	49.71	
		Sum	2372.11			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-20 17:20:38+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A1
Acq. method: Run ID 5% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** ID
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.649	MM m	0.47	337.03	47.84	95.34	
3.277	MM m	0.30	16.46	1.85	4.66	
Sum			353.49			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-26 14:38:23+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run ID 5% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** ID
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1F,Sig=240,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.644	MM m	0.29	145.43	20.52	50.91	
3.216	MM m	0.46	140.21	14.75	49.09	
Sum			285.64			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-10 17:08:22+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.606	MM m	0.35	254.43	31.24	94.60	
2.193	MM m	0.32	14.54	1.66	5.40	
Sum			268.97			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-12 18:16:22+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.575	MM m	0.28	109.96	16.32	50.80	
2.129	MM m	0.42	106.48	11.60	49.20	
Sum			216.44			

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	7.72 min	5586.6892	95.625
2	8.77 min	255.5972	4.375

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	7.79 min	3524.4238	51.094
2	8.9 min	3373.5015	48.906

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-14 16:11:57+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 6% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1F,Sig=240,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.650	MM m	0.26	233.89	59.41	94.55	
2.551	MM m	0.22	13.48	2.32	5.45	
Sum			247.37			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-16 14:27:18+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-C9
Acq. method: Run IF 6% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.650	MM m	0.29	217.38	56.85	50.10	
2.541	MM m	0.39	216.48	35.94	49.90	
Sum			433.86			

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
3p methanol	15	MeOH	OD-H	DFO467	11F	32.7	4	3	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	96.5394	19136.7958	11.08 min	521.8873	0
2	3.4606	685.9882	12.52 min	26.0198	0

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
3p methanol	15	MeOH	OD-H	DFO467	11F	29.7	4	3	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	49.6586	4075.2342	11.78 min	95.9262	0
2	50.3414	4131.2627	13.48 min	78.3299	0

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	6.87 min	12734.0751	95.0686
2	7.92 min	660.5474	4.9314

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
1	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	7.02 min	7641.9698	51.4718
2	7.97 min	7204.9401	48.5282

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-27 13:12:01+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1F,Sig=240,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.961	MM m	0.40	1798.37	240.02	96.47	
3.651	MM m	0.51	65.79	5.10	3.53	
		Sum	1864.16			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-27 12:51:12+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1F,Sig=240,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.948	MM m	0.42	912.25	114.43	49.15	
3.587	MM m	0.61	943.96	69.81	50.85	
		Sum	1856.21			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-20 12:15:14+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A1
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1E,Sig=230,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.599	MM m	0.54	752.33	86.55	93.99	
5.875	MM m	0.68	48.09	2.36	6.01	
Sum			800.42			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-08-26 14:51:06+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-B9
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.675	MM m	0.46	533.27	61.05	50.18	
6.005	MM m	0.89	529.38	26.87	49.82	
Sum			1062.65			

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
1.5p methanol	15	MeOH	OJ-H	DFO351	11E	29.9	4	1.5	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	96.4958	15632.5768	9.17 min	510.3518	0
2	3.5042	567.6957	10.97 min	23.0074	0

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
1.5p methanol	15	MeOH	OJ-H	DFO451	11F	30.8	4	1.5	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	50.8704	803.7574	8.27 min	25.3205	0
2	49.1296	776.2522	9.86 min	22.0339	0

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
2p methanol	15	MeOH	OD-H	DFO459	11F	29.7	4	2	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	1.9696	168.5283	4.07 min	10.9582	4073.95
2	98.0304	8387.9094	5.02 min	357.7055	5023.9333

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
2p methanol	15	MeOH	OD-H	DFO459	11E	29.4	4	2	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	51.5416	1745.2535	3.72 min	83.5015	3715.6167
2	48.4584	1640.8516	4.81 min	58.5151	4807.2667

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IA 4% MeOH 10 minutes.amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-09-15 19:18:45+02:00
Location: D1F-A9
Type: Sample
Column: IA

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.359	MM m	0.29	24.78	3.04	3.87	
2.699	MM m	0.57	616.37	58.05	96.13	
Sum			641.15			

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IA 4% MeOH 10 minutes.amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-09-15 16:44:49+02:00
Location: D1F-A9
Type: Sample
Column: IA

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
0.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	5.82 min	7523.428	93.6119
2	6.68 min	513.3982	6.3881

Co-Solvent %	Total Flow	Column	Co-Solvent	Back Pressure
0.5	4	OJ-H	MeOH	150

Peak #	Ret. Time	Area	Area %
1	6.17 min	5112.9186	49.7175
2	6.99 min	5171.0172	50.2825

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-08-26 18:29:41+02:00
Location: D1F-A9
Type: Sample
Column: IF

Signal: MWD1D,Sig=220,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.054	MM m	0.48	566.06	73.07	88.61	
2.792	MM m	0.56	72.76	5.87	11.39	
Sum			638.82			

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-09-17 16:47:49+02:00
Location: D1F-A9
Type: Sample
Column: IF

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
2.112	MM m	0.38	290.97	41.68	49.72	
2.774	MM m	0.61	294.22	26.03	50.28	
Sum			585.19			

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
1.5p methanol	10	MeOH	OJ-H	DFO110	13D	29.3	4	1.5	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	98.4956	5424.9916	4.42 min	229.809	4415.6
2	1.5044	82.8574	5.27 min	5.4419	5265.6

Run Information

Instrument Method	Inj. Vol.	Solvent	Column	Sample	Well Location	Temp.	Flow	% Modifier	Pressure
1.5p methanol	10	MeOH	OJ-H	DFO110	11A	31.1	4	1.5	150

Peak Information

Peak No	% Area	Area	Ret. Time	Height	Cap. Factor
1	49.8884	3599.2591	4.21 min	176.2016	4207.2833
2	50.1116	3615.3575	5.07 min	167.5883	5073.9333

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-08-26 17:37:17+02:00
Location: D1F-A9
Type: Sample
Column: IF

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
3.161	MM m	0.61	1015.92	114.99	95.54	
5.360	MM m	0.66	47.48	3.01	4.46	
Sum			1063.40			

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IF 3% MeOH 10 minutes.amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-08-26 15:22:51+02:00
Location: D1F-E9
Type: Sample
Column: IF

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
3.198	MM m	0.40	548.75	62.28	51.00	
5.365	MM m	0.88	527.30	30.16	49.00	
Sum			1076.05			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-13 13:30:48+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-B9
Acq. method: Run IF 6% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.914	MM m	0.26	827.18	171.82	96.51	
2.951	MM m	0.23	29.89	4.64	3.49	
Sum			857.07			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-13 13:08:46+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-A9
Acq. method: Run IF 6% MeOH 10 minutes.amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration.pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.913	MM m	0.28	492.88	103.81	48.36	
2.928	MM m	0.32	526.29	70.60	51.64	
Sum			1019.17			

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IF 9% MeOH 10 minutes,amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration,pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-08-27 15:23:02+02:00
Location: D1F-A9
Type: Sample
Column: IF

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
3.319	MM m	0.43	1969.22	312.44	96.55	
3.896	MM m	0.30	70.35	10.43	3.45	
Sum			2039.57			

Instrument: SFC
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL
Acq. method: Run IF 9% MeOH 10 minutes,amx
Processing method: *Manual Integration,pmx
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Injection date: 2021-09-04 11:50:04+02:00
Location: D1F-B9
Type: Sample
Column: IF

Signal: MWD1B,Sig=250,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
3.321	MM m	0.52	1486.26	256.69	50.48	
3.874	MM m	0.53	1457.72	216.11	49.52	
Sum			2943.98			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-04 14:31:01+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-D9
Acq. method: Run IF 9% MeOH 10 minutes,amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration,pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1E,Sig=230,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.343	MM m	0.20	213.22	63.79	18.73	
1.972	MM m	0.45	924.97	168.84	81.27	
		Sum	1138.19			

Instrument: SFC **Injection date:** 2021-09-17 17:00:32+02:00
Inj. volume: 2.000 µL **Location:** D1F-B9
Acq. method: Run IF 9% MeOH 10 minutes,amx **Type:** Sample
Processing method: *Manual Integration,pmx **Column:** IF
Manually modified: Manual Integration

Signal: MWD1G,Sig=260,4 Ref=360,100

RT [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area	Height	Area%	Name
1.345	MM m	0.15	27.85	8.58	49.86	
1.974	MM m	0.27	28.01	5.38	50.14	
		Sum	55.87			

Signal 2: DAD1 B, Sig=210,16 Ref=360,100

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	14.464	MM	0.6069	1050.07654	28.83551	25.3463
2	15.747	MM	0.6043	3092.84766	85.30321	74.6537

Signal 2: DAD1 B, Sig=210,16 Ref=360,100

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	14.718	BV	0.4925	1576.63892	42.92902	45.8326
2	16.074	VB	0.4863	1863.35913	49.82269	54.1674

Signal 3: DAD1 D, Sig=230,16 Ref=360,100

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	18.003	MM	0.5750	3730.04175	108.10882	16.9066
2	19.838	MM	0.6239	1.83326e4	489.72440	83.0934

Signal 3: DAD1 D, Sig=230,16 Ref=360,100

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	17.277	MM	0.5776	8786.87402	253.52759	49.5120
2	19.173	MM	0.6220	8960.08105	240.07440	50.4880

Signal 1: DAD1 A, Sig=254,4 Ref=360,100

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	12.336	MF	0.4063	15.84537	6.49940e-1	4.9364
2	13.223	FM	0.4095	305.14343	12.41816	95.0636

Signal 1: DAD1 A, Sig=254,4 Ref=360,100

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	12.901	MF	0.3988	71.08186	2.97103	48.0188
2	13.912	FM	0.4257	76.94743	3.01243	51.9812

17. Crystallographic data of compound **3o**

Experimental. Single colourless prism-shaped crystals of **3o** were used as supplied. A suitable crystal with dimensions $0.19 \times 0.04 \times 0.03 \text{ mm}^3$ was selected and mounted on a SuperNova, Dual, Cu at home/near, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at a steady $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$ during data collection. The structure was solved with the **ShelXT** 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) solution program using dual methods and by using **Olex2** 1.5 (Dolomanov et al., 2009) as the graphical interface. The model was refined with **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015) using full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 .

Crystal Data. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_2$, $M_r = 351.24$, monoclinic, $P2_1$ (No. 4), $a = 5.14830(18) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 10.3849(4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 15.3727(6) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 93.918(3)^\circ$, $\alpha = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 819.97(5) \text{ \AA}^3$, $T = 140.00(10) \text{ K}$, $Z = 2$, $Z' = 1$, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 3.465$, 12176 reflections measured, 3162 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0424$) which were used in all calculations. The final wR_2 was 0.1025 (all data) and R_1 was 0.0378 ($I \geq 2\sigma(I)$).

Compound	3o
Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₂
Dcalc	1.423
μ/mm^{-1}	3.465
Formula Weight	351.24
Colour	colourless
Shape	prism-shaped
Size/mm ³	0.19×0.04×0.03
T/K	140.00(10)
Crystal System	monoclinic
Flack Parameter	-0.05(3)
Space Group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁
<i>a</i> /Å	5.14830(18)
<i>b</i> /Å	10.3849(4)
<i>c</i> /Å	15.3727(6)
$\alpha/^\circ$	90
$\beta/^\circ$	93.918(3)
$\gamma/^\circ$	90
<i>V</i> /Å ³	819.97(5)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>Z</i> '	1
Wavelength/Å	1.54184
Radiation type	CuK α
$\theta_{\text{min}}/^\circ$	2.881
$\theta_{\text{max}}/^\circ$	72.872
Measured Refl's.	12176
Indep't Refl's	3162
Refl's $I \geq 2\sigma(I)$	3016
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.0424
Parameters	197
Restraints	1
Largest Peak/e Å ⁻³	0.573
Deepest Hole/e Å ⁻³	-0.398
GooF	1.042
<i>wR</i> ₂ (all data)	0.1025
<i>wR</i> ₂	0.1003
<i>R</i> ₁ (all data)	0.0397
<i>R</i> ₁	0.0378
<i>CCDC number</i>	2108325

Structure Quality Indicators

Reflections:	d min (Cu α) 2 θ =145.7°	0.81	<i>I</i> / σ (<i>I</i>) CIF	31.2	<i>R</i> _{int} CIF	4.24%	Full 135.4° 98% to 145.7°	99.9		
Refinement:	Shift CIF	0.000	Max Peak CIF	0.6	Min Peak CIF	-0.4	GooF CIF	1.042	Hoofit CIF	-0.05(3)

A colourless prism-shaped-shaped crystal with dimensions 0.19 × 0.04 × 0.03 mm³ was mounted. Data were collected using a SuperNova, Dual, Cu at home/near, Atlas diffractometer operating at *T* = 140.00(10) K.

Data were measured using ω scans with Cu K α radiation. The diffraction pattern was indexed and the total number of runs and images was based on the strategy calculation from the program CrysAlisPro

1.171.41.116a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The maximum resolution achieved was $\theta = 72.872^\circ$ (0.81 Å).

The unit cell was refined using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku OD, 2021) on 8718 reflections, 72% of the observed reflections.

Data reduction, scaling and absorption corrections were performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku OD, 2021). The final completeness is 99.90 % out to 72.872° in θ . A Gaussian absorption correction was performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.41.116a (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, 2021) Numerical absorption correction based on Gaussian integration over a multifaceted crystal model. Empirical absorption correction using spherical harmonics as implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm. The absorption coefficient μ of this material is 3.465 mm^{-1} at this wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) and the minimum and maximum transmissions are 0.564 and 1.000.

The structure was solved and the space group $P2_1$ (# 4) determined by the ShelXT 2018/2 (Sheldrick, 2015) structure solution program using dual methods and refined by full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 using version 2018/3 of **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015). All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Most hydrogen atom positions were calculated geometrically and refined using the riding model, but the hydrogen atom bound to N1 was refined freely.

There is a single molecule in the asymmetric unit, which is represented by the reported sum formula. In other words: Z is 2 and Z' is 1.

The Flack parameter was refined to -0.05(3). Determination of absolute structure using Bayesian statistics on Bijvoet differences using the Olex2 results in None. Note: The Flack parameter is used to determine chirality of the crystal studied, the value should be near 0, a value of 1 means that the stereochemistry is wrong and the model should be inverted. A value of 0.5 means that the crystal consists of a racemic mixture of the two enantiomers.

Citations

CrysAlis^{Pro} Software System, Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, (2021).

Sheldrick, G.M., ShelXT-Integrated space-group and crystal-structure determination, *Acta Cryst.*, (2015), **A71**, 3-8.

Sheldrick, G.M., Crystal structure refinement with ShelXL, *Acta Cryst.*, (2015), **C71**, 3-8.

O.V. Dolomanov and L.J. Bourhis and R.J. Gildea and J.A.K. Howard and H. Puschmann, **Olex2**: A complete structure solution, refinement and analysis program, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, (2009), **42**, 339-341.

Figure S4: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Figure S5: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Figure S6: Image of the Crystal on the Diffractometer.

Data Plots: Diffraction Data

Data Plots: Refinement and Data

Reflection Statistics

Total reflections (after filtering)	12200	Unique reflections	3162
Completeness	0.967	Mean I/σ	23.44
$hkl_{\max}$ collected	(6, 12, 18)	$hkl_{\min}$ collected	(-6, -12, -18)
$hkl_{\max}$ used	(6, 12, 18)	$hkl_{\min}$ used	(-6, -12, 0)
Lim $d_{\max}$ collected	100.0	Lim $d_{\min}$ collected	0.77
$d_{\max}$ used	15.34	$d_{\min}$ used	0.81
Friedel pairs	2703	Friedel pairs merged	0
Inconsistent equivalents	9	R_{int}	0.0424
R_{sigma}	0.0321	Intensity transformed	0
Omitted reflections	0	Omitted by user (OMIT hkl)	0
Multiplicity	(2036, 2106, 1096, 463, 133, 21, 3)	Maximum multiplicity	11
Removed systematic absences	24	Filtered off (Shel/OMIT)	0

Table S9: Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **3o**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
Br1	-737.1(8)	2130.4(5)	4573.8(3)	36.34(18)
O1	2426(7)	6125(4)	8339(2)	34.6(8)
O2	5490(6)	6402(4)	9470(2)	30.1(7)
N1	6738(8)	5867(4)	8175(3)	29.0(8)
N2	10018(9)	2884(5)	7496(3)	41.3(11)

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
C1	4675(9)	6129(5)	8640(3)	26.8(9)
C2	6417(10)	5696(5)	7244(3)	30.0(10)
C3	5995(11)	4279(6)	6946(4)	27.5(12)
C4	8234(9)	3489(5)	7267(3)	29.6(10)
C5	5691(11)	4275(6)	5964(4)	27.9(12)
C6	3505(10)	3974(5)	5506(3)	27.3(9)
C7	3108(10)	4130(5)	4553(3)	28.9(10)
C8	1242(10)	3432(5)	4048(3)	32.1(10)
C9	848(13)	3613(6)	3159(4)	41.4(13)
C10	2333(17)	4495(7)	2751(4)	52.3(17)
C11	4224(17)	5184(7)	3223(5)	47.9(17)
C12	4574(13)	5030(6)	4112(4)	36.4(14)
C13	3600(10)	6689(5)	10127(3)	29.4(10)
C14	5369(10)	6941(8)	10938(3)	43.6(16)
C15	2023(11)	7879(5)	9868(4)	37.9(12)
C16	1905(10)	5523(5)	10254(4)	32.5(11)

Table S10: Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\times 10^4$) for **3o**. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2[h^2a^{*2} \times U_{11} + \dots + 2hka^* \times b^* \times U_{12}]$

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
Br1	28.5(3)	39.6(3)	40.5(3)	-10.0(3)	-0.51(18)	-0.2(3)
O1	18.3(15)	56(2)	29.2(18)	-3.3(16)	-2.5(13)	-1.3(15)
O2	15.6(15)	49(2)	26.2(17)	-8.7(15)	3.6(12)	0.8(14)
N1	17.4(18)	46(2)	23(2)	-5.3(17)	-0.4(16)	-0.9(17)
N2	33(2)	48(3)	42(3)	12(2)	-2(2)	0(2)
C1	20(2)	36(2)	24(2)	-1.4(18)	-0.7(17)	-0.6(18)
C2	30(2)	37(2)	23(2)	0.6(19)	2.2(19)	0(2)
C3	22(3)	40(3)	20(2)	3.4(19)	0(2)	-2(2)
C4	25(2)	38(2)	25(2)	7.4(19)	0.2(19)	-6(2)
C5	25(3)	36(3)	24(3)	0(2)	3(2)	-2(2)
C6	24(2)	33(2)	24(2)	-2.6(17)	1.6(18)	-0.3(18)
C7	30(3)	33(2)	24(2)	0.8(18)	-0.7(19)	6.9(19)
C8	32(2)	32(2)	31(3)	-4.5(19)	-4(2)	8(2)
C9	48(3)	40(3)	33(3)	-6(2)	-14(2)	11(2)
C10	77(5)	54(4)	24(3)	3(2)	-6(3)	14(3)
C11	60(4)	47(4)	38(4)	12(3)	3(3)	2(3)
C12	39(4)	38(3)	31(3)	5(2)	1(3)	5(3)
C13	22(2)	38(2)	29(2)	-6.2(18)	9.4(19)	0.3(18)
C14	25(2)	76(5)	29(2)	-19(3)	4.4(18)	-1(3)
C15	29(3)	31(3)	55(3)	-3(2)	11(2)	0(2)
C16	25(2)	36(3)	37(3)	7(2)	5(2)	6.2(19)

Table S11: Bond Lengths in Å for **3o**.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Br1	C8	1.905(6)
O1	C1	1.217(6)
O2	C1	1.346(6)
O2	C13	1.480(5)

Atom	Atom	Length/Å
N1	C1	1.348(6)
N1	C2	1.442(6)
N2	C4	1.149(7)
C2	C3	1.552(8)
C3	C4	1.472(7)
C3	C5	1.507(8)
C5	C6	1.324(8)
C6	C7	1.474(7)
C7	C8	1.396(7)
C7	C12	1.404(8)
C8	C9	1.381(8)
C9	C10	1.372(10)
C10	C11	1.374(11)
C11	C12	1.376(10)
C13	C14	1.515(7)
C13	C15	1.517(7)
C13	C16	1.513(7)

Table S12: Bond Angles in ° for **3o**.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C1	O2	C13	120.8(4)
C1	N1	C2	120.7(4)
O1	C1	O2	126.0(4)
O1	C1	N1	124.1(5)
O2	C1	N1	109.8(4)
N1	C2	C3	114.5(4)
C4	C3	C2	109.8(5)
C4	C3	C5	111.1(4)
C5	C3	C2	107.5(5)
N2	C4	C3	178.0(5)
C6	C5	C3	124.1(5)
C5	C6	C7	123.9(5)
C8	C7	C6	122.6(5)
C8	C7	C12	116.7(5)
C12	C7	C6	120.7(5)
C7	C8	Br1	120.0(4)
C9	C8	Br1	118.0(4)
C9	C8	C7	121.9(5)
C10	C9	C8	119.6(6)
C9	C10	C11	120.2(6)
C10	C11	C12	120.2(7)
C11	C12	C7	121.2(6)
O2	C13	C14	102.1(4)
O2	C13	C15	110.5(4)
O2	C13	C16	109.8(4)
C14	C13	C15	110.8(5)
C16	C13	C14	110.6(5)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C16	C13	C15	112.5(4)

Table S13: Torsion Angles in ° for **3o**.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
Br1	C8	C9	C10	-176.6(5)
N1	C2	C3	C4	-59.2(5)
N1	C2	C3	C5	179.9(4)
C1	O2	C13	C14	-179.5(5)
C1	O2	C13	C15	-61.5(6)
C1	O2	C13	C16	63.2(6)
C1	N1	C2	C3	-92.6(6)
C2	N1	C1	O1	6.8(8)
C2	N1	C1	O2	-172.5(4)
C2	C3	C5	C6	-113.0(6)
C3	C5	C6	C7	171.8(5)
C4	C3	C5	C6	126.8(6)
C5	C6	C7	C8	157.4(5)
C5	C6	C7	C12	-24.3(7)
C6	C7	C8	Br1	-4.6(6)
C6	C7	C8	C9	178.3(5)
C6	C7	C12	C11	179.9(6)
C7	C8	C9	C10	0.5(8)
C8	C7	C12	C11	-1.7(9)
C8	C9	C10	C11	0.8(10)
C9	C10	C11	C12	-2.5(11)
C10	C11	C12	C7	3.0(11)
C12	C7	C8	Br1	177.1(4)
C12	C7	C8	C9	0.0(7)
C13	O2	C1	O1	2.4(8)
C13	O2	C1	N1	-178.3(4)

Table S14: Hydrogen Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **3o**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H1	8270(140)	5900(60)	8420(40)	30(15)
H2A	7980.6	6035.98	6981.24	36
H2B	4906.68	6213.77	7014.96	36
H3	4372.09	3936.42	7183.88	33
H5	7159.99	4502.16	5655.06	34
H6	2108.98	3636.49	5808.7	33
H9	-444.89	3129.46	2831.33	50
H10	2052.91	4629.9	2140.99	63
H11	5293.61	5768.09	2933.76	58
H12	5830.95	5542.08	4434.27	44
H14A	6448.2	6180.11	11071.3	65
H14B	4311.15	7126.26	11429.07	65
H14C	6491.54	7680.99	10836.64	65
H15A	3199.15	8572.78	9715.54	57

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H15B	1030.63	8153.61	10357.72	57
H15C	819.42	7680.01	9364.76	57
H16A	889.99	5327.32	9707.81	49
H16B	720.23	5702.16	10712.08	49
H16C	3007.41	4783.55	10425.8	49

Table S15: Hydrogen Bond information for **3o**.

D	H	A	d(D-H)/Å	d(H-A)/Å	d(D-A)/Å	D-H-A/deg
N1	H1	O1 ¹	0.85(7)	2.16(7)	2.934(5)	151(6)

¹1+x, +y, +z

18. Crystallographic data of compound F

Experimental. Single clear pale colourless needle-shaped crystals of **F** were used as supplied. A suitable crystal with dimensions $0.20 \times 0.03 \times 0.02$ mm³ was selected and mounted on a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer. The crystal was kept at a steady $T = 140.00(10)$ K during data collection. The structure was solved with the **ShelXT** (Sheldrick, 2015) solution program using dual methods and by using **Olex2** 1.5 (Dolomanov et al., 2009) as the graphical interface. The model was refined with **ShelXL** 2018/3 (Sheldrick, 2015) using full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 .

Crystal Data. C₂₄H₂₀CuN₃O₂, $M_r = 445.97$, orthorhombic, $P2_12_12$ (No. 18), $a = 8.44624(13)$ Å, $b = 46.7029(8)$ Å, $c = 10.9780(2)$ Å, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 4330.43(13)$ Å³, $T = 140.00(10)$ K, $Z = 8$, $Z' = 2$, $\mu(\text{Cu } K\alpha) = 1.620$, 27194 reflections measured, 8196 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0355$) which were used in all calculations. The final wR_2 was 0.0855 (all data) and R_1 was 0.0388 ($I \geq 2 \sigma(I)$).

Compound	F
Formula	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ CuN ₃ O ₂
<i>D</i> _{calc.} / g cm ⁻³	1.368
μ /mm ⁻¹	1.620
Formula Weight	445.97
Colour	clear pale colourless
Shape	needle-shaped
Size/mm ³	0.20×0.03×0.02
<i>T</i> /K	140.00(10)
Crystal System	orthorhombic
Flack Parameter	-0.009(11)
Hoof Parameter	-0.009(11)
Space Group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2
<i>a</i> /Å	8.44624(13)
<i>b</i> /Å	46.7029(8)
<i>c</i> /Å	10.9780(2)
α /°	90
β /°	90
γ /°	90
<i>V</i> /Å ³	4330.43(13)
<i>Z</i>	8
<i>Z</i> '	2
Wavelength/Å	1.54184
Radiation type	Cu K α
Θ _{min} /°	3.786
Θ _{max} /°	74.722
Measured Refl's.	27194
Indep't Refl's	8196
Refl's I $\geq$ 2 σ (I)	6655
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.0355
Parameters	642
Restraints	383
Largest Peak	0.239
Deepest Hole	-0.313
Goof	1.023
<i>wR</i> ₂ (all data)	0.0855
<i>wR</i> ₂	0.0787
<i>R</i> ₁ (all data)	0.0562
<i>R</i> ₁	0.0388

Structure Quality Indicators

Reflections:	d min (Cu α) 2 Θ =149.4°	0.80	I/ σ (I)	21.7	<i>R</i> _{int}	3.55%	Full 135.4° 97% to 149.4°	100		
Refinement:	Shift	-0.001	Max Peak	0.2	Min Peak	-0.3	Goof	1.023	Hoof	-0.009(11)

A clear pale colourless needle-shaped crystal with dimensions 0.20 × 0.03 × 0.02 mm³ was mounted. Data were collected using a XtaLAB Synergy R, DW system, HyPix-Arc 150 diffractometer operating at *T* = 140.00(10) K.

Data were measured using ω scans with Cu K α radiation. The diffraction pattern was indexed and the total number of runs and images was based on the strategy calculation from the program CrysAlisPro

1.171.42.82a (Rigaku OD, 2023). The maximum resolution that was achieved was $\theta = 74.722^\circ$ (0.80 Å).

The unit cell was refined using CrysAlisPro 1.171.42.82a (Rigaku OD, 2023) on 9950 reflections, 37% of the observed reflections.

Data reduction, scaling and absorption corrections were performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.42.82a (Rigaku OD, 2023). The final completeness is 100.00 % out to 74.722° in θ . An analytical absorption correction was performed using CrysAlisPro 1.171.42.82a (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction, 2023). The analytical numeric absorption correction was done using a multifaceted crystal model based on expressions derived by R.C. Clark & J.S. Reid. (Clark, R. C. & Reid, J. S. (1995). Acta Cryst. A51, 887-897). The empirical absorption correction was carried out using spherical harmonics, implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm. The absorption coefficient μ of this crystal is 1.620 mm^{-1} at this wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54184 \text{ \AA}$) and the minimum and maximum transmissions are 0.782 and 0.976.

The structure was solved and the space group $P2_12_12$ (# 18) determined by the ShelXT (Sheldrick, 2015) structure solution program using dual methods and refined by full matrix least squares minimisation on F^2 using version 2018/3 of **ShelXL** (Sheldrick, 2015). All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atom positions were calculated geometrically and refined using the riding model.

_smtbx_masks_special_details: A solvent mask was calculated and 132 electrons were found in a volume of $572 \text{ \AA}^3$ in 1 void per unit cell. This is consistent with the presence of 1[CH₃OH] per Asymmetric Unit which account for 144 electrons per unit cell.

The value of Z' is 2. This means that there are two independent molecules in the asymmetric unit.

The Flack parameter was refined to -0.009(11). Determination of absolute structure using Bayesian statistics on Bijvoet differences using the Olex2 results in -0.009(11). Note: The Flack parameter is used to determine chirality of the crystal studied, the value should be near 0, a value of 1 means that the stereochemistry is wrong and the model should be inverted. A value of 0.5 means that the crystal consists of a racemic mixture of the two enantiomers.

Data Plots: Diffraction Data

Data Plots: Refinement and Data

Reflection Statistics

Total reflections (after filtering)	27281	Unique reflections	8196
Completeness	0.92	Mean I/σ	18.48
$hkl_{\max}$ collected	(10, 58, 12)	$hkl_{\min}$ collected	(-9, -57, -13)
$hkl_{\max}$ used	(10, 58, 13)	$hkl_{\min}$ used	(-10, 0, 0)
Lim $d_{\max}$ collected	100.0	Lim $d_{\min}$ collected	0.77
$d_{\max}$ used	15.57	$d_{\min}$ used	0.8
Friedel pairs	3136	Friedel pairs merged	0
Inconsistent equivalents	1	R_{int}	0.0355
R_{sigma}	0.046	Intensity transformed	0
Omitted reflections	0	Omitted by user (OMIT hkl)	0
Multiplicity	(11020, 3384, 1261, 744, 309, Maximum multiplicity)		13
Removed systematic absences	87	Filtered off (Shel/OMIT)	0

Table S16: Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for **F**. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
Cu1	7904.0(7)	6818.0(2)	4468.7(6)	28.30(15)
O1	7113(4)	6121.2(6)	2195(3)	40.4(8)
O2	5556(4)	7072.1(6)	1287(3)	35.7(8)
N1	7663(4)	6442.7(7)	3660(3)	27.9(8)
N2	6638(4)	7014.3(7)	3137(3)	23.5(7)
N3	9264(5)	7085.1(9)	6730(4)	39.1(10)
C1	8177(5)	6164.7(8)	4179(4)	32.8(10)
C2	7157(5)	6068.6(9)	5218(4)	34.8(11)
C3	7005(6)	6193.7(10)	6364(4)	41.1(11)
C4	5972(7)	6071.7(13)	7208(6)	55.6(16)
C5	5129(6)	5827.5(14)	6892(6)	59.3(18)
C6	5271(6)	5706.3(12)	5777(6)	51.3(15)
C7	6302(5)	5826.1(9)	4917(5)	41.1(12)
C8	6676(7)	5726.5(10)	3648(5)	52.2(14)
C9	7842(6)	5946.4(9)	3157(4)	37.3(11)
C10	7093(5)	6393.9(8)	2602(4)	26.6(9)
C11	6365(5)	6598.9(9)	1751(4)	27.5(10)
C12	6227(5)	6901.2(8)	2133(4)	25.0(9)
C13	5374(6)	7357.0(9)	1834(4)	32.5(11)
C14	6209(6)	7583.4(9)	1070(4)	34.5(11)
C15	7721(5)	7638.7(8)	1747(4)	29.7(10)
C16	9004(6)	7807.7(10)	1408(5)	43.2(13)
C17	10289(6)	7834.7(10)	2192(5)	46.0(14)
C18	10297(6)	7697.5(9)	3297(5)	41.0(13)
C19	9011(5)	7531.3(9)	3664(5)	32.0(10)
C20	7745(5)	7503.5(8)	2871(4)	25.0(9)
C21	6272(5)	7325.3(8)	3048(4)	24.0(9)
C22	8774(5)	6972.0(9)	5877(4)	27.6(10)
C23	5044(5)	6484.5(10)	924(4)	33.3(11)
C24	6611(5)	6541.9(9)	384(4)	35.6(11)
Cu02	11728.6(8)	5863.7(2)	4948.2(6)	36.71(17)
O3	12958(4)	6681.1(6)	6163(3)	32.2(7)
O4	10189(4)	5993.9(7)	8508(3)	39.2(8)
N4	12438(4)	6269.4(7)	5180(3)	27.3(8)
N5	10775(4)	5853.5(8)	6597(4)	32.0(9)
N6	11690(50)	5470(6)	2760(20)	87(5)
N7	12310(70)	5548(10)	2630(40)	71(7)
C25	13244(5)	6448.9(9)	4266(4)	30.5(10)
C26	12216(5)	6526.2(9)	3208(4)	29.9(10)
C27	11619(6)	6347.7(10)	2312(4)	33.9(11)
C28	10721(5)	6466.9(10)	1384(4)	35.9(11)
C29	10423(5)	6760.4(10)	1363(4)	34.9(11)
C30	11001(5)	6938.1(10)	2266(4)	32.0(10)
C31	11898(5)	6819.3(9)	3197(4)	28.2(9)
C32	12625(5)	6968.9(9)	4293(4)	31.2(10)
C33	13560(5)	6735.2(9)	4934(4)	32.3(10)
C34	12340(5)	6416.2(9)	6176(4)	26.3(9)
C35	11656(5)	6327.9(9)	7335(4)	26.3(9)
C36	10864(5)	6046.4(9)	7418(4)	28.8(10)
C37	9618(18)	5693(2)	8422(17)	41(3)
C38	10503(14)	5488(2)	9277(12)	44(2)
C39	11375(13)	5290(2)	8429(12)	43(2)
C40	12416(12)	5066(2)	8752(12)	48(3)

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
C41	13084(13)	4910(2)	7818(13)	49(3)
C42	12746(12)	4965(2)	6581(13)	48(2)
C43	11727(14)	5187(2)	6282(11)	41(2)
C44	11055(18)	5347(3)	7223(10)	38(2)
C45	9950(20)	5600(3)	7110(19)	39(2)
C46	9340(40)	5720(5)	8470(30)	41(3)
C47	10030(20)	5542(5)	9530(20)	43(4)
C48	11100(20)	5345(4)	8860(20)	43(3)
C49	12080(20)	5125(4)	9270(20)	51(4)
C50	12980(30)	4963(4)	8460(20)	50(4)
C51	12870(30)	4981(4)	7210(20)	47(3)
C52	11840(30)	5195(5)	6780(20)	45(3)
C53	10980(40)	5367(6)	7580(20)	40(3)
C54	9950(40)	5616(6)	7240(40)	40(3)
C55	11860(50)	5622(6)	3604(19)	56(4)
C56	11730(120)	5660(15)	3490(40)	63(6)
C57	12540(5)	6426.6(9)	8479(4)	33.1(11)
C58	11026(6)	6565.9(10)	8173(4)	34.2(11)

Table S17: Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\times 10^4$) for F. The anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2[h^2a^{*2} \times U_{11} + \dots + 2hka^* \times b^* \times U_{12}]$

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
Cu1	26.6(3)	32.7(3)	25.6(3)	0.4(3)	-3.5(3)	-2.9(3)
O1	52(2)	25.1(14)	44(2)	-1.5(13)	-18.5(18)	0.4(15)
O2	52(2)	27.1(15)	28.0(18)	0.7(14)	-11.8(16)	-0.8(15)
N1	24.6(18)	27.7(17)	31(2)	3.2(16)	-4.8(17)	-2.3(15)
N2	22.4(17)	26.3(17)	21.9(18)	0.8(14)	-0.8(15)	-1.1(15)
N3	40(2)	44(2)	34(2)	-5(2)	-8(2)	2.8(19)
C1	27(2)	29(2)	42(3)	4.6(19)	-7(2)	0.5(19)
C2	29(2)	34(2)	42(3)	12(2)	-8(2)	2.8(19)
C3	35(3)	49(3)	39(3)	12(2)	-6(3)	2(2)
C4	47(3)	72(4)	48(4)	24(3)	-5(3)	12(3)
C5	31(3)	73(4)	73(5)	45(4)	-3(3)	-4(3)
C6	37(3)	47(3)	70(4)	26(3)	-17(3)	-6(2)
C7	32(2)	32(2)	59(3)	16(3)	-12(3)	0.6(19)
C8	61(3)	30(2)	65(4)	4(3)	-10(3)	-4(3)
C9	41(3)	27(2)	43(3)	3(2)	-8(3)	6(2)
C10	27(2)	23.1(19)	30(2)	-1.2(17)	-5(2)	-3.5(18)
C11	30(2)	27(2)	25(2)	0.5(18)	-6(2)	-3.1(18)
C12	24(2)	28(2)	23(2)	5.1(18)	-4.9(18)	-1.0(16)
C13	41(3)	26(2)	30(3)	3(2)	-5(2)	1(2)
C14	51(3)	31(2)	22(2)	0.9(19)	2(2)	2(2)
C15	43(3)	22.6(19)	24(2)	-2.4(17)	9(2)	2.1(19)
C16	64(3)	31(2)	34(3)	0(2)	22(3)	1(2)
C17	44(3)	35(3)	58(4)	-3(3)	17(3)	-11(2)
C18	35(3)	31(2)	57(4)	-4(2)	4(3)	-13(2)
C19	33(2)	30(2)	34(3)	-1(2)	2(2)	-2.9(19)
C20	28(2)	23.6(18)	23(2)	-1.6(17)	8(2)	-1.8(18)
C21	25(2)	26(2)	21(2)	0.3(18)	3.0(18)	1.0(17)
C22	23(2)	30(2)	29(3)	4(2)	-2.9(19)	0.4(18)
C23	37(2)	31(2)	32(3)	-1(2)	-10(2)	-4(2)
C24	42(3)	38(2)	27(3)	-7(2)	-8(2)	-5(2)
Cu02	43.7(4)	31.6(3)	34.9(4)	-5.2(3)	-8.5(3)	7.2(3)

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
O3	39.3(17)	34.9(15)	22.2(16)	-1.5(12)	1.5(15)	-9.0(15)
O4	45.1(19)	39.9(18)	32.5(19)	8.0(15)	5.4(17)	-8.1(15)
N4	27.9(18)	32.2(17)	22(2)	0.4(15)	-3.3(15)	4.9(14)
N5	28.4(19)	28.2(18)	40(2)	0.5(19)	-8.0(17)	0.4(17)
N6	126(13)	66(9)	69(8)	-28(7)	-23(9)	21(9)
N7	107(16)	59(13)	47(10)	-28(10)	-11(12)	30(11)
C25	25(2)	39(2)	27(2)	1.2(19)	5(2)	3.8(19)
C26	29(2)	37(2)	23(2)	0.7(18)	6(2)	4(2)
C27	39(3)	40(2)	23(2)	-3(2)	2(2)	1(2)
C28	36(3)	49(3)	22(3)	-2(2)	3(2)	-2(2)
C29	31(2)	47(3)	26(3)	6(2)	2(2)	5(2)
C30	32(2)	35(2)	29(3)	3(2)	7(2)	-1(2)
C31	26(2)	34(2)	25(2)	2.5(19)	6.4(19)	-1(2)
C32	33(2)	34(2)	27(2)	0.4(19)	3(2)	-10.1(19)
C33	27(2)	45(2)	25(2)	0(2)	5(2)	-5.6(18)
C34	23(2)	29(2)	26(2)	-0.8(18)	-4.4(19)	-0.6(17)
C35	25(2)	30(2)	24(2)	0.7(18)	-2(2)	0.6(18)
C36	27(2)	33(2)	26(3)	6(2)	-5(2)	1.9(19)
C37	29(5)	43(4)	51(5)	13(4)	-6(5)	-11(4)
C38	37(5)	40(4)	54(5)	12(4)	-2(4)	-5(4)
C39	32(4)	36(4)	62(6)	12(4)	-2(4)	-10(3)
C40	32(5)	38(5)	74(6)	15(5)	-4(5)	-6(4)
C41	27(4)	39(4)	81(8)	12(5)	-6(5)	-5(3)
C42	32(4)	35(3)	77(7)	11(5)	0(5)	-7(3)
C43	35(4)	33(3)	54(5)	7(4)	-1(5)	-4(3)
C44	28(3)	32(4)	54(5)	10(4)	-8(5)	-12(3)
C45	30(4)	35(4)	51(5)	5(4)	-11(4)	-4(3)
C46	31(6)	43(6)	49(6)	10(5)	-5(6)	-10(5)
C47	33(7)	40(6)	56(7)	13(6)	-4(6)	-5(6)
C48	29(5)	35(5)	65(6)	12(5)	-8(5)	-5(5)
C49	35(6)	41(6)	77(8)	14(6)	-7(7)	-5(5)
C50	30(6)	42(7)	79(8)	10(7)	-4(7)	0(6)
C51	31(5)	40(5)	69(7)	9(6)	-3(6)	-7(5)
C52	31(5)	38(5)	65(7)	11(6)	-9(6)	-13(4)
C53	29(4)	34(5)	56(6)	11(5)	-7(5)	-8(4)
C54	30(5)	35(5)	55(6)	9(6)	-8(6)	-5(5)
C55	88(9)	38(8)	44(6)	-10(6)	-28(6)	35(6)
C56	94(13)	48(13)	46(9)	-14(10)	-21(10)	24(11)
C57	42(3)	33(2)	24(2)	-1.2(19)	-6(2)	-3(2)
C58	45(3)	34(2)	23(2)	-3(2)	10(2)	-4(2)

Table S18: Bond Lengths in Å for F.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Cu1	N1	1.976(3)
Cu1	N2	2.030(3)
Cu1	C22	1.857(5)
O1	C9	1.470(5)
O1	C10	1.350(5)
O2	C12	1.349(5)
O2	C13	1.468(5)
N1	C1	1.483(5)
N1	C10	1.277(5)
N2	C12	1.271(5)
N2	C21	1.488(5)
N3	C22	1.152(6)

Atom	Atom	Length/Å
C1	C2	1.499(6)
C1	C9	1.542(6)
C2	C3	1.393(7)
C2	C7	1.383(6)
C3	C4	1.395(7)
C4	C5	1.389(8)
C5	C6	1.354(8)
C6	C7	1.401(7)
C7	C8	1.502(7)
C8	C9	1.522(7)
C10	C11	1.472(6)
C11	C12	1.478(6)
C11	C23	1.534(6)
C11	C24	1.537(6)
C13	C14	1.523(6)
C13	C21	1.540(6)
C14	C15	1.500(6)
C15	C16	1.391(6)
C15	C20	1.386(6)
C16	C17	1.391(8)
C17	C18	1.372(7)
C18	C19	1.394(6)
C19	C20	1.385(6)
C20	C21	1.509(6)
C23	C24	1.475(6)
Cu02	N4	2.003(3)
Cu02	N5	1.982(4)
Cu02	C55	1.863(10)
Cu02	C56	1.86(2)
O3	C33	1.464(5)
O3	C34	1.343(5)
O4	C36	1.347(5)
O4	C37	1.491(11)
O4	C46	1.466(18)
N4	C25	1.474(5)
N4	C34	1.293(5)
N5	C36	1.276(6)
N5	C45	1.485(11)
N5	C54	1.490(19)
N6	C55	1.17(2)
N7	C56	1.19(6)
C25	C26	1.495(6)
C25	C33	1.548(6)
C26	C27	1.385(6)
C26	C31	1.395(6)
C27	C28	1.387(6)
C28	C29	1.394(6)
C29	C30	1.382(6)
C30	C31	1.389(6)
C31	C32	1.520(6)
C32	C33	1.520(6)
C34	C35	1.457(6)
C35	C36	1.478(6)
C35	C57	1.532(6)
C35	C58	1.538(6)
C37	C38	1.534(11)

Atom	Atom	Length/Å
C37	C45	1.530(12)
C38	C39	1.504(12)
C39	C40	1.414(11)
C39	C44	1.377(12)
C40	C41	1.378(11)
C41	C42	1.411(11)
C42	C43	1.387(11)
C43	C44	1.396(11)
C44	C45	1.508(12)
C46	C47	1.54(2)
C46	C54	1.53(2)
C47	C48	1.487(19)
C48	C49	1.393(16)
C48	C53	1.407(19)
C49	C50	1.392(16)
C50	C51	1.377(16)
C51	C52	1.411(17)
C52	C53	1.397(17)
C53	C54	1.503(19)
C57	C58	1.474(6)

Table S19: Bond Angles in ° for F.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
N1	Cu1	N2	91.30(14)
C22	Cu1	N1	139.35(17)
C22	Cu1	N2	129.29(16)
C10	O1	C9	106.9(3)
C12	O2	C13	107.4(3)
C1	N1	Cu1	125.0(3)
C10	N1	Cu1	127.3(3)
C10	N1	C1	107.7(3)
C12	N2	Cu1	125.5(3)
C12	N2	C21	106.9(3)
C21	N2	Cu1	126.7(3)
N1	C1	C2	112.7(4)
N1	C1	C9	104.2(3)
C2	C1	C9	104.5(4)
C3	C2	C1	128.0(4)
C7	C2	C1	111.3(4)
C7	C2	C3	120.7(5)
C2	C3	C4	119.1(5)
C5	C4	C3	119.3(6)
C6	C5	C4	121.6(6)
C5	C6	C7	119.8(5)
C2	C7	C6	119.4(5)
C2	C7	C8	111.4(4)
C6	C7	C8	129.2(5)
C7	C8	C9	104.8(4)
O1	C9	C1	103.5(3)
O1	C9	C8	111.0(4)
C8	C9	C1	107.9(4)
O1	C10	C11	114.1(4)
N1	C10	O1	117.7(4)
N1	C10	C11	128.2(4)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C10	C11	C12	118.3(4)
C10	C11	C23	116.9(4)
C10	C11	C24	116.8(4)
C12	C11	C23	116.3(4)
C12	C11	C24	117.0(4)
C23	C11	C24	57.4(3)
O2	C12	C11	113.8(4)
N2	C12	O2	117.8(4)
N2	C12	C11	128.5(4)
O2	C13	C14	110.8(4)
O2	C13	C21	102.4(3)
C14	C13	C21	108.4(4)
C15	C14	C13	103.9(4)
C16	C15	C14	128.9(4)
C20	C15	C14	112.0(4)
C20	C15	C16	119.0(4)
C17	C16	C15	119.6(5)
C18	C17	C16	120.5(5)
C17	C18	C19	120.8(5)
C20	C19	C18	118.2(4)
C15	C20	C21	110.7(4)
C19	C20	C15	121.8(4)
C19	C20	C21	127.4(4)
N2	C21	C13	104.7(3)
N2	C21	C20	112.1(3)
C20	C21	C13	104.0(3)
N3	C22	Cu1	175.3(4)
C24	C23	C11	61.4(3)
C23	C24	C11	61.2(3)
N5	Cu02	N4	91.62(15)
C55	Cu02	N4	131.1(14)
C55	Cu02	N5	137.2(15)
C56	Cu02	N4	126(3)
C56	Cu02	N5	141(3)
C34	O3	C33	107.7(3)
C36	O4	C37	104.6(8)
C36	O4	C46	110.0(16)
C25	N4	Cu02	126.1(3)
C34	N4	Cu02	126.1(3)
C34	N4	C25	107.7(3)
C36	N5	Cu02	127.1(3)
C36	N5	C45	108.9(9)
C36	N5	C54	102.8(17)
C45	N5	Cu02	123.8(9)
C54	N5	Cu02	129.8(16)
N4	C25	C26	113.5(3)
N4	C25	C33	104.4(3)
C26	C25	C33	105.0(3)
C27	C26	C25	128.2(4)
C27	C26	C31	121.0(4)
C31	C26	C25	110.8(4)
C26	C27	C28	118.7(4)
C27	C28	C29	120.4(5)
C30	C29	C28	121.0(4)
C29	C30	C31	118.8(4)
C26	C31	C32	111.5(4)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C30	C31	C26	120.2(4)
C30	C31	C32	128.3(4)
C33	C32	C31	104.3(3)
O3	C33	C25	103.1(3)
O3	C33	C32	111.7(3)
C32	C33	C25	108.1(4)
O3	C34	C35	115.1(4)
N4	C34	O3	117.0(4)
N4	C34	C35	127.8(4)
C34	C35	C36	119.0(4)
C34	C35	C57	115.9(4)
C34	C35	C58	117.1(4)
C36	C35	C57	115.9(4)
C36	C35	C58	116.7(4)
C57	C35	C58	57.4(3)
O4	C36	C35	114.1(4)
N5	C36	O4	118.3(4)
N5	C36	C35	127.7(4)
O4	C37	C38	113.0(9)
O4	C37	C45	105.5(12)
C45	C37	C38	108.0(12)
C39	C38	C37	104.0(9)
C40	C39	C38	127.2(10)
C44	C39	C38	112.4(9)
C44	C39	C40	120.4(10)
C41	C40	C39	117.4(9)
C40	C41	C42	122.4(9)
C43	C42	C41	119.4(9)
C42	C43	C44	118.5(9)
C39	C44	C43	121.9(10)
C39	C44	C45	110.5(11)
C43	C44	C45	127.5(11)
N5	C45	C37	102.5(13)
N5	C45	C44	111.5(12)
C44	C45	C37	105.0(13)
O4	C46	C47	105.7(18)
O4	C46	C54	98(2)
C54	C46	C47	112(2)
C48	C47	C46	101.0(18)
C49	C48	C47	131.1(18)
C49	C48	C53	115(2)
C53	C48	C47	113.7(16)
C50	C49	C48	121.1(18)
C51	C50	C49	124.5(19)
C50	C51	C52	114.9(18)
C53	C52	C51	120.9(19)
C48	C53	C54	111(2)
C52	C53	C48	123(2)
C52	C53	C54	126(2)
N5	C54	C46	110(2)
N5	C54	C53	115(2)
C53	C54	C46	102(2)
N6	C55	Cu02	169(4)
N7	C56	Cu02	155(9)
C58	C57	C35	61.5(3)
C57	C58	C35	61.1(3)

Table S20: Torsion Angles in ° for F.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
Cu1	N1	C1	C2	71.5(4)
Cu1	N1	C1	C9	-175.7(3)
Cu1	N1	C10	O1	176.5(3)
Cu1	N1	C10	C11	-4.9(7)
Cu1	N2	C12	O2	-172.0(3)
Cu1	N2	C12	C11	8.7(6)
Cu1	N2	C21	C13	176.8(3)
Cu1	N2	C21	C20	64.7(4)
O1	C10	C11	C12	177.6(4)
O1	C10	C11	C23	30.7(6)
O1	C10	C11	C24	-34.5(5)
O2	C13	C14	C15	-101.7(4)
O2	C13	C21	N2	-8.7(4)
O2	C13	C21	C20	109.0(4)
N1	C1	C2	C3	-67.0(6)
N1	C1	C2	C7	112.7(4)
N1	C1	C9	O1	-2.4(5)
N1	C1	C9	C8	-120.1(4)
N1	C10	C11	C12	-1.1(7)
N1	C10	C11	C23	-148.0(5)
N1	C10	C11	C24	146.9(5)
C1	N1	C10	O1	-1.6(5)
C1	N1	C10	C11	177.0(4)
C1	C2	C3	C4	179.4(4)
C1	C2	C7	C6	-179.6(4)
C1	C2	C7	C8	1.3(5)
C2	C1	C9	O1	116.1(4)
C2	C1	C9	C8	-1.6(5)
C2	C3	C4	C5	0.5(7)
C2	C7	C8	C9	-2.3(5)
C3	C2	C7	C6	0.2(6)
C3	C2	C7	C8	-179.0(4)
C3	C4	C5	C6	-0.8(8)
C4	C5	C6	C7	0.7(8)
C5	C6	C7	C2	-0.4(7)
C5	C6	C7	C8	178.5(5)
C6	C7	C8	C9	178.7(4)
C7	C2	C3	C4	-0.2(7)
C7	C8	C9	O1	-110.4(4)
C7	C8	C9	C1	2.3(5)
C9	O1	C10	N1	-0.1(6)
C9	O1	C10	C11	-178.9(4)
C9	C1	C2	C3	-179.5(4)
C9	C1	C2	C7	0.2(5)
C10	O1	C9	C1	1.6(5)
C10	O1	C9	C8	117.1(4)
C10	N1	C1	C2	-110.3(4)
C10	N1	C1	C9	2.4(5)
C10	C11	C12	O2	179.5(4)
C10	C11	C12	N2	-1.3(7)
C10	C11	C23	C24	-105.9(4)
C10	C11	C24	C23	106.2(4)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C12	O2	C13	C14	123.3(4)
C12	O2	C13	C21	7.9(4)
C12	N2	C21	C13	6.8(4)
C12	N2	C21	C20	-105.3(4)
C12	C11	C23	C24	106.5(4)
C12	C11	C24	C23	-105.4(4)
C13	O2	C12	N2	-4.2(5)
C13	O2	C12	C11	175.1(4)
C13	C14	C15	C16	173.7(4)
C13	C14	C15	C20	-8.3(5)
C14	C13	C21	N2	-125.9(4)
C14	C13	C21	C20	-8.1(4)
C14	C15	C16	C17	178.7(4)
C14	C15	C20	C19	-178.3(4)
C14	C15	C20	C21	3.4(5)
C15	C16	C17	C18	-0.4(7)
C15	C20	C21	N2	115.5(4)
C15	C20	C21	C13	3.0(4)
C16	C15	C20	C19	-0.2(6)
C16	C15	C20	C21	-178.4(4)
C16	C17	C18	C19	-0.8(7)
C17	C18	C19	C20	1.4(7)
C18	C19	C20	C15	-0.9(6)
C18	C19	C20	C21	177.0(4)
C19	C20	C21	N2	-62.6(5)
C19	C20	C21	C13	-175.1(4)
C20	C15	C16	C17	0.9(6)
C21	N2	C12	O2	-1.9(5)
C21	N2	C12	C11	178.9(4)
C21	C13	C14	C15	9.9(5)
C23	C11	C12	O2	-33.4(5)
C23	C11	C12	N2	145.8(4)
C24	C11	C12	O2	31.6(5)
C24	C11	C12	N2	-149.2(4)
Cu02	N4	C25	C26	67.9(4)
Cu02	N4	C25	C33	-178.3(3)
Cu02	N4	C34	O3	176.6(3)
Cu02	N4	C34	C35	-2.3(6)
Cu02	N5	C36	O4	-177.1(3)
Cu02	N5	C36	C35	2.0(7)
Cu02	N5	C45	C37	174.0(7)
Cu02	N5	C45	C44	62.2(17)
Cu02	N5	C54	C46	-176.9(14)
Cu02	N5	C54	C53	68(4)
O3	C34	C35	C36	176.5(4)
O3	C34	C35	C57	-37.8(5)
O3	C34	C35	C58	27.1(5)
O4	C37	C38	C39	-114.1(13)
O4	C37	C45	N5	3.3(14)
O4	C37	C45	C44	119.9(11)
O4	C46	C47	C48	-102(2)
O4	C46	C54	N5	-11(3)
O4	C46	C54	C53	111(2)
N4	Cu02	C55	N6	-116(13)
N4	Cu02	C56	N7	64(12)
N4	C25	C26	C27	-67.7(6)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
N4	C25	C26	C31	112.8(4)
N4	C25	C33	O3	2.3(4)
N4	C25	C33	C32	-116.2(4)
N4	C34	C35	C36	-4.6(7)
N4	C34	C35	C57	141.1(4)
N4	C34	C35	C58	-154.0(4)
N5	Cu02	C55	N6	58(13)
N5	Cu02	C56	N7	-134(12)
C25	N4	C34	O3	-0.3(5)
C25	N4	C34	C35	-179.2(4)
C25	C26	C27	C28	-178.0(4)
C25	C26	C31	C30	178.0(4)
C25	C26	C31	C32	-2.6(5)
C26	C25	C33	O3	121.9(4)
C26	C25	C33	C32	3.5(4)
C26	C27	C28	C29	-0.3(7)
C26	C31	C32	C33	4.7(5)
C27	C26	C31	C30	-1.5(7)
C27	C26	C31	C32	177.9(4)
C27	C28	C29	C30	-0.5(7)
C28	C29	C30	C31	0.4(7)
C29	C30	C31	C26	0.6(6)
C29	C30	C31	C32	-178.6(4)
C30	C31	C32	C33	-176.0(4)
C31	C26	C27	C28	1.3(7)
C31	C32	C33	O3	-117.7(4)
C31	C32	C33	C25	-4.8(4)
C33	O3	C34	N4	1.9(5)
C33	O3	C34	C35	-179.0(3)
C33	C25	C26	C27	178.9(4)
C33	C25	C26	C31	-0.5(5)
C34	O3	C33	C25	-2.5(4)
C34	O3	C33	C32	113.4(4)
C34	N4	C25	C26	-115.1(4)
C34	N4	C25	C33	-1.3(4)
C34	C35	C36	O4	-176.1(4)
C34	C35	C36	N5	4.8(7)
C34	C35	C57	C58	106.8(4)
C34	C35	C58	C57	-104.8(4)
C36	O4	C37	C38	113.3(11)
C36	O4	C37	C45	-4.6(12)
C36	O4	C46	C47	124.8(18)
C36	O4	C46	C54	9(2)
C36	N5	C45	C37	-0.8(13)
C36	N5	C45	C44	-112.6(12)
C36	N5	C54	C46	9(3)
C36	N5	C54	C53	-106(3)
C36	C35	C57	C58	-106.4(4)
C36	C35	C58	C57	105.0(4)
C37	O4	C36	N5	4.6(7)
C37	O4	C36	C35	-174.6(6)
C37	C38	C39	C40	177.9(10)
C37	C38	C39	C44	-2.5(12)
C38	C37	C45	N5	-117.9(11)
C38	C37	C45	C44	-1.3(14)
C38	C39	C40	C41	179.7(10)

Atom	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C38	C39	C44	C43	-179.3(12)
C38	C39	C44	C45	1.8(15)
C39	C40	C41	C42	-0.8(14)
C39	C44	C45	N5	110.0(15)
C39	C44	C45	C37	-0.3(15)
C40	C39	C44	C43	0.3(17)
C40	C39	C44	C45	-178.6(11)
C40	C41	C42	C43	1.1(14)
C41	C42	C43	C44	-0.7(15)
C42	C43	C44	C39	0.0(18)
C42	C43	C44	C45	178.6(13)
C43	C44	C45	N5	-69(2)
C43	C44	C45	C37	-179.0(13)
C44	C39	C40	C41	0.1(14)
C45	N5	C36	O4	-2.5(10)
C45	N5	C36	C35	176.6(9)
C45	C37	C38	C39	2.2(12)
C46	O4	C36	N5	-4.8(13)
C46	O4	C36	C35	176.0(13)
C46	C47	C48	C49	-179(2)
C46	C47	C48	C53	-7(2)
C47	C46	C54	N5	-122(2)
C47	C46	C54	C53	1(3)
C47	C48	C49	C50	179(2)
C47	C48	C53	C52	-177(2)
C47	C48	C53	C54	8(3)
C48	C49	C50	C51	-7(3)
C48	C53	C54	N5	114(3)
C48	C53	C54	C46	-5(3)
C49	C48	C53	C52	-4(4)
C49	C48	C53	C54	-178(2)
C49	C50	C51	C52	5(3)
C50	C51	C52	C53	-2(3)
C51	C52	C53	C48	1(4)
C51	C52	C53	C54	175(3)
C52	C53	C54	N5	-61(4)
C52	C53	C54	C46	-180(3)
C53	C48	C49	C50	6(3)
C54	N5	C36	O4	-2.8(16)
C54	N5	C36	C35	176.2(15)
C54	C46	C47	C48	3(2)
C57	C35	C36	O4	38.2(5)
C57	C35	C36	N5	-140.9(5)
C58	C35	C36	O4	-26.6(5)
C58	C35	C36	N5	154.3(4)

Table S21: Hydrogen Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for F. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} .

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
H1	9323	6167.35	4407.49	39
H3	7597.71	6359.83	6567.98	49
H4	5846.51	6154.84	7992.29	67
H5	4436.31	5743.43	7472.2	71
H6	4672.66	5540.45	5578.58	62

Atom	x	y	z	<i>U</i>_{eq}
H8A	5705.8	5720.68	3142.51	63
H8B	7156.8	5533.22	3661.99	63
H9	8838.71	5853.31	2865.94	45
H13	4234.84	7405.93	1968.8	39
H14A	6426.62	7511.34	238.31	41
H14B	5563.46	7759.74	1011.42	41
H16	9001.85	7904.11	645.97	52
H17	11169.4	7949.03	1959.98	55
H18	11188.41	7715.95	3818.58	49
H19	9003.27	7439.71	4436.13	38
H21	5627.66	7393.48	3754.41	29
H23A	4724.65	6281.96	1026.41	40
H23B	4168.75	6616.6	714.42	40
H24A	6712.63	6709.78	-160.43	43
H24B	7268.61	6375.09	151.61	43
H25	14255.01	6358.44	3989.29	37
H27	11820.65	6147.63	2332.21	41
H28	10305.88	6347.86	758.9	43
H29	9812.85	6839.43	718.05	42
H30	10788.98	7137.8	2248.86	38
H32A	13329.31	7126.87	4032.48	37
H32B	11792.62	7047.17	4833.32	37
H33	14716.47	6781.09	4948.88	39
H37	8454.69	5684.44	8589.19	49
H38A	11250.42	5594.23	9805.3	52
H38B	9753.4	5380.28	9796.85	52
H40	12646.94	5024.01	9579.98	57
H41	13797.11	4759.3	8014.65	59
H42	13212.07	4851.19	5960.06	58
H43	11492.62	5229.21	5454.82	49
H45	8961.9	5551.37	6654.05	46
H46	8166.6	5741.25	8509.07	49
H47A	10615.05	5662.84	10114.24	52
H47B	9187.13	5435.31	9965.69	52
H49	12135.72	5085.25	10119.03	61
H50	13719.57	4831.16	8794.98	60
H51	13444.08	4857.63	6683.87	56
H52	11725.57	5223.15	5925.7	54
H54	9036.61	5546.53	6731.48	48
H57A	12555.93	6295.29	9186.51	40
H57B	13522.22	6539.15	8363.36	40
H58A	11063.69	6765.08	7865.99	41
H58B	10097.14	6521.15	8689.35	41

Table S22: Atomic Occupancies for all atoms that are not fully occupied in **F**.

Atom	Occupancy
N6	0.67(7)
N7	0.33(7)
C37	0.649(15)
H37	0.649(15)
C38	0.649(15)
H38A	0.649(15)
H38B	0.649(15)
C39	0.649(15)
C40	0.649(15)

Atom	Occupancy
H40	0.649(15)
C41	0.649(15)
H41	0.649(15)
C42	0.649(15)
H42	0.649(15)
C43	0.649(15)
H43	0.649(15)
C44	0.649(15)
C45	0.649(15)
H45	0.649(15)
C46	0.351(15)
H46	0.351(15)
C47	0.351(15)
H47A	0.351(15)
H47B	0.351(15)
C48	0.351(15)
C49	0.351(15)
H49	0.351(15)
C50	0.351(15)
H50	0.351(15)
C51	0.351(15)
H51	0.351(15)
C52	0.351(15)
H52	0.351(15)
C53	0.351(15)
C54	0.351(15)
H54	0.351(15)
C55	0.67(7)
C56	0.33(7)

Table S23: Solvent masking (PLATON/SQUEEZE) information for **F**.

No	x	y	z	V	e	Content
1	-0.640	0.000	-0.167	286.5	66.0	4MeOH
2	-0.071	0.500	0.167	286.5	66.7	4MeOH